

WGBS Pipeline

Crow WGBS pipeline for analyzing 2 male and 2 female hooded crows (*Corvus corone cornix*), for which we have a spleen and liver tissue.

PAR Coverage

```
#!/bin/bash

#SBATCH --get-user-env
#SBATCH --mail-user=merondun@bio.lmu.de
#SBATCH --clusters=biohpc_gen
#SBATCH --partition=biohpc_gen_production
#SBATCH --cpus-per-task=3
#SBATCH --mem-per-cpu=4763mb
#SBATCH --time=12:00:00

#positional arguments
RUN=$1
SAMPLE=$2
R1=$3
R2=$4

rawdat=/dss/dss1egfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-0018/rawdata/WGS/Illumina/POPseq
wd=/dss/dss1egfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-0018/projects/2021__HybridZone_Epigenetics/Crow_W_PAR_ID
genome=$wd/chrZ.w.5.fa

SCRATCH=tmp/$SLURM_JOB_ID
mkdir tmp
mkdir $SCRATCH
mkdir $wd/trim
mkdir $wd/bam
mkdir $wd/coverage

#adapter trim
bbduk.sh t=8 -Xmx30g in=${rawdat}/${R1} in2=${rawdat}/${R2}
out=$wd/trim/${RUN}.trim.fastq.gz minlen=25 qtrim=r1 trimq=2 ktrim=r k=23 mink=11
ref=~/.modules/bbmap/adapters.fa hdist=1 tpe tbo

#assign read groups
ID=${RUN}
SM=${SAMPLE}
LB=${SM}
PU=${RUN}

#alignment
bwa mem -M -p -t 10 -R "@RG\tID:${ID}\tSM:${SM}\tPL:ILLUMINA\tLB:${LB}\tPU:${PU}"
${genome} $wd/trim/${RUN}.trim.fastq.gz | samtools sort -@10 -o
$SCRATCH/${RUN}.raw.bam -;

samtools view -b -f 1 -F 1536 $SCRATCH/${RUN}.raw.bam > ${wd}/bam/${RUN}.bam
samtools index -b ${wd}/bam/${RUN}.bam
```

```
#coverage
mosdepth --threads 5 --use-median --by 100000 --fast-mode --no-per-base
${wd}/coverage/${RUN} ${wd}/bam/${RUN}.bam
```

Merge output beds:

```
#take the unzipped bed.gz file from mosdepth, and change it into the below
for i in $(ls *.regions.bed | rev | cut -c13- | rev); do awk -v s=${i}
'BEGIN{print s}; {print $4}' ${i}.regions.bed > ${i}.cov; done

#create header file with chr / start / end, since all files on the same genome,
they all have the same length and this is consistent across samples
awk '{OFS="\t"}BEGIN{print "CHR","START","END"};{print $1, $2, $3}'
D_Ko_c20_AD10TUACXX-L001.regions.bed | sed 's/\ /&#92;/g' > 0001Header.cov

#combine them all together..
paste *.cov > Master.coverage
```

And Plot:

```
#### MANHATTAN COVERAGE
setwd('/dss/dsslegfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-
0018/projects/2021__HybridZone_Epigenetics/Crow_W_PAR_ID/')

source('~/modules/R_Functions.R')
library(dplyr)
library(karyoploteR)
library(tidyr)
library(maditr)
library(RColorBrewer)
library(viridis)
#library(yarrrr)
library(LICORS)
library(ggplot2)
library(scales)

#init legwork
class <- read.table('Master.coverage',header=TRUE)
#take only individuals with known sex
cls <- class[,c(1,2,3,18,19,20,21,22,23)]
clsm <- melt(cls,id.vars=c('CHR','START','END'))
#separate ID into simpler format
clsm <- as.data.frame(clsm) %>% separate(variable, into =
c('ID1','ID2','ID3','Flowcell','Lane'))
#subset only cols of interest
cls <- clsm[,c('CHR','START','END','ID3','value')]
#import sex data
sex <- read.table('Sex_meta.txt',header=F)
names(sex) <- c('ID3','SEX')
cl <- merge(cls,sex,by='ID3')
#calculate median chromosome-wide
chrs <- cl %>% group_by(ID3,CHR) %>% summarize(median(value)) %>% subset(CHR ==
'chr5')
```

```

names(chrs) <- c('ID3','CHR','MEDIAN5')
#now we will add this value of chr5 median to all values of the dataset for
normalization
chr <- chrs[,c('ID3','MEDIAN5')]
#re-merge
c <- merge(c1,chr,by='ID3')
#calculate normalized values and add sex colors
c <- c %>% mutate(Normalized = value / MEDIAN5,
                 color = ifelse(SEX == 'm', 'dodgerblue', 'mediumpurple'))

#Set up genome
genome <- read.table('chrZ.W.5.genome',header=FALSE)
crowG <- makeGRangesFromDataFrame(genome,seqnames.field = 'v1',start.field =
'v2',end.field = 'v3')

##### PLOT: Manhattan, will require commenting out depending on what you want..
#####
png('Whole-Genome.Manhattan-NoHI.png',height=6,width=10,units='in',res=600,bg =
"transparent")
pdf('Whole-Genome.Manhattan.pdf',height=6,width=10)
pdf('Chr18.Manhattan.pdf',height=5,width=6)
png('Chr18.Manhattan-NoHI.png',height=5,width=6,units='in',res=600,bg =
"transparent")

#Plot Base
pp <- getDefaultPlotParams(plot.type=4)
pp$leftmargin <- 0.08
kp <- plotKaryotype(plot.type=4, genome = crowG)
kpAddBaseNumbers(kp,tick.dist = 25000000)

run <- 'c'
#tracks <- ncol(class[,-c(1:3)])
tracks <- 6

counter <- 0
for (varz in unique(c$ID3)) {
  counter <- counter+1
  cat('Current Autotrack: ',counter,' for ',varz,'\n')
  dat <- c[grep1(varz,c$ID3),]
  at <- autotrack(current.track = counter, total.tracks = tracks);
  at$r1 <- at$r1-0.01
  #add coverage
  kpPoints(kp, col=dat$Color, chr = dat$CHR, x=dat$START,
y=dat$Normalized,ymin=0,ymax=2,r0=at$r0,r1=at$r1);
  kpAbline(kp, h=1, r0=at$r0, r1=at$r1, ymin=0,ymax=2,col="grey30", lwd=1,lty=2)
  kpAxis(kp, cex=0.5,r0=at$r0, r1=at$r1, ymin=0,ymax=2,col="black", lwd=1,lty=1)
  #add bottom lines
  kpAbline(kp, h=0, r0=at$r0, r1=at$r1, ymin=0,ymax=2,col='black', lwd=1,lty=1)
}
kpAddLabels(kp,'chrN / chr5 Normalized
value',cex=0.75,srt=90,r0=0.4,label.margin=0.03)

```

PAR Synteny

We will do several (7) syntenic analyses, with the crowZ PAR as our focus:

- Whole sequence PAR (688KB) <> Syntenic W assembly (scaffs = 227) #A
- Whole sequence PAR (688KB) <> New caledonian crow Z+W chrom #B
- Whole sequence PAR (688KB) <> Flycatcher PAR Genes #C
- Flycatcher PAR Genes <> New caledonian crow Z+W chrom #D
- PAR Genes <> Syntenic W assembly (scaffs = 227) #E
- PAR Genes <> New caledonian crow Z+W #F
- PAR Genes <> Flycatcher PAR Genes #G

```
#cat PAR.bed
#chrZ    1        688000
#extract PAR sequence
seqkit subseq --bed PAR.bed chrZ.fa > PAR.fa

#extract PAR genes
seqkit subseq --bed Genes-PAR.bed chrZ.fa > PAR-GENES.fa
#Clean up headers so only gene name is left
sed -i 's/chrZ.*:. //' PAR-GENES.fa

#Grab only Z+W from NCC assembly, and clean up names
seqtk subseq GCF_009650955.1_bCorMon1.pri_genomic.fna NCC-W.name > NCC-ZW.fa
sed -i 's/NC_045510.1.*sequence/NCC_chrW/' NCC-ZW.fa
sed -i 's/NC_045511.1.*sequence/NCC_chrZ/' NCC-ZW.fa

#clean up FLY, remove everything after the first pipe
sed -i 's/|.*//' PAR_genes_.flycatcher.fa
```

And submit all jobs:

```
#!/bin/bash

#SBATCH --get-user-env
#SBATCH --mail-user=merondun@bio.lmu.de
#SBATCH --clusters=biohpc_gen
#SBATCH --partition=biohpc_gen_normal
#SBATCH --cpus-per-task=5
#SBATCH --mem-per-cpu=4763mb
#SBATCH --time=12:00:00

PAR=PAR.fa
PARG=PAR-GENES.fa
wsyn=wscaffs_syntenyOnly.fa
Flycatch=PAR_genes_.flycatcher.fa
NCC=NCC-ZW.fa

##
lastz $PAR $wsyn \
--notransition --step=20 --nogapped --format=general > lastz/PAR-wsyn.out
```

```

#B#
lastz $PAR $NCC \
--notransition --step=20 --nogapped --format=general > lastz/PAR-NCC.out

#C#
lastz $PAR $Flycatch \
--notransition --step=20 --nogapped --format=general > lastz/PAR-FLY.out

#D#
lastz $Flycatch[multiple] $NCC \
--notransition --step=20 --nogapped --format=general > lastz/FLY-NCC.out

#E#
lastz $PARG[multiple] $wsyn \
--notransition --step=20 --nogapped --format=general > lastz/PARG-WSYN.out

#F#
lastz $PARG[multiple] $Flycatch \
--notransition --step=20 --nogapped --format=general > lastz/PARG-FLY.out

#G#
lastz $PARG[multiple] $NCC \
--notransition --step=20 --nogapped --format=general > lastz/PARG-NCC.out

```

Prepare it for plotting:

```

#grab name/start/end/name2/start2/end2 and add a custom link color
for i in $(ls *out | sed 's/.out//g'); do

awk -v s=${i} '{OFS="\t"}{print $2, $5, $6, $6-$5, $7,$10,
$11,$11-$10,$12,$13,$14, $15, "color="s}' ${i}.out | \
    grep -v 'zstart' | awk '$10 > 70 && $4 > 1000' | cut -f4,8,9,10,11,12 --
complement \
    > ${i}.1KB-P70.bed

awk -v s=${i} '{OFS="\t"}{print $2, $5, $6, $6-$5, $7,$10,
$11,$11-$10,$12,$13,$14, $15, "color="s}' ${i}.out | \
    grep -v 'zstart' | cut -f4,8,9,10,11,12 --complement \
    > ${i}.all.bed

done

#now swap our IDs with specific colors
sed -i 's/wScaff'
sed -i 's/FLY-NCC/black/g' FLY-NCC.bed
sed -i 's/PAR-FLY/grey/g' PAR-FLY.bed
sed -i 's/PARG-FLY/orange/g' PARG-FLY.bed
sed -i 's/PARG-NCC/purple/g' PARG-NCC.bed
sed -i 's/PARG-WSYN/green/g' PARG-WSYN.bed
sed -i 's/PAR-NCC/yellow/g' PAR-NCC.bed
sed -i 's/PAR-WSYN/blue/g' PAR-WSYN.bed

```

Create circos karyotype file from samtools .fai:

```

for i in $(ls *fai | sed 's/.fa.fai//g'); do
awk -v s=${i} '{OFS="\t"}{print "chr","-", $1, $1, "0", $2, s}' ${i}.fa.fai >
${i}.karyo
done

#and swap the ideograms with colors
sed -i 's/NCC-ZW/black/g' NCC-ZW.karyo
sed -i 's/PAR_genes_.flycatcher/grey/g' PAR_genes_.flycatcher.karyo
sed -i 's/PAR-GENES/orange/g' PAR-GENES.karyo
sed -i 's/PAR/purple/g' PAR.karyo
sed -i 's/wscaffs_syntenonly/green/g' wscaffs_syntenonly.karyo
#ensure you manually check

```

Within circos.conf:

```

# circos.conf

#karyotype = Crow-PAR-Syntenic.karyo.txt
#karyotype = Crow-PAR-Syntenic-NOScaffolds.karyo.txt
karyotype = PAR-Genes_NCC_FLY.karyo.txt
#karyotype = PAR_WScaff.karyo.txt
#karyotype = PAR_NCC_FLY.karyo.txt

<ideogram>

<spacing>
default = 0.005r
</spacing>

radius    = 0.8r
thickness = 20p
fill      = yes

show_label    = yes
# see etc/fonts.conf for list of font names
label_font    = default
label_radius  = 1r + 75p
label_size    = 25
label_parallel = no

</ideogram>

<links>

<link>
file        = Master-Syntenic-PAR.txt
radius      = 0.95r
bezier_radius = 0.1r
thickness   = 3
</link>

</links>

```

```
#####
# The remaining content is standard and required. It is imported
# from default files in the Circos distribution.
#
# These should be present in every Circos configuration file and
# overridden as required. To see the content of these files,
# look in etc/ in the Circos distribution.

<image>
# Included from Circos distribution.
<<include etc/image.conf>>
</image>

# RGB/HSV color definitions, color lists, location of fonts, fill patterns.
# Included from Circos distribution.
<<include etc/colors_fonts_patterns.conf>>

# Debugging, I/O and other system parameters
# Included from Circos distribution.
<<include housekeeping.conf>>
```


Chr23 Synteny

```
#!/bin/bash
```

```

#SBATCH --get-user-env
#SBATCH --mail-user=merondun@bio.lmu.de
#SBATCH --clusters=biohpc_gen
#SBATCH --partition=biohpc_gen_normal
#SBATCH --cpus-per-task=15
#SBATCH --mem-per-cpu=4763mb
#SBATCH --time=48:00:00

#genome-based files
genomedir=/dss/dsslegfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-
0018/projects/2021__HybridZone_Epigenetics/Genomes/Corvus_5.6
genome=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.fasta

#subest sequence
#seqtk subseq $genome chr23.list > chr23_segment.fa

lastz chr23_segment.fa $genome \
--notransition --step=20 --nogapped --format=general > lastz/chr23.out

```

```

setwd('~/.files/')
source('~/.modules/R_Functions.R')
library(dplyr)
library(karyoploteR)
library(tidyr)
library(maditr)
library(RColorBrewer)
library(viridis)
library(LICORS)
library(ggplot2)
library(scales)

#read synteny
wza <- read.table('chr23.out',header=T)
wza$idPct <- gsub('%',' ',wza$idPct)
wza$idPct <- as.numeric(wza$idPct)
wza$length <- abs(wza$zstart1-wza$end1)
wza$length2 <- abs(wza$zstart2-wza$end2)
wz <- subset(wza,idPct > 70)
wz <- subset(wz,length > 500)

#Set up genome
genome <- read.table('genome5.6.bed',header=FALSE)
genome$lab <- gsub('chr',' ',genome$V1)
genome$lab <- gsub('A',' ',genome$lab)
genome$lab <- gsub('Z','100',genome$lab)
genome <- genome %>% arrange(as.integer(lab))
genome$start <- 1
cG <- makeGRangesFromDataFrame(genome,seqnames.field = 'V1',start.field =
'start',end.field = 'V2')

##### Plot synteny + coverage
png('Synteny-chr23_corvus5.6.png',height=5,width=10,units='in',res=600,bg =
"white")

#Plot Base

```

```

pp <- getDefaultPlotParams(plot.type=1)
kp <- plotKaryotype(plot.type=4, genome = cG)
kpAddBaseNumbers(kp,tick.dist = 25000000)

#add Z-w links
wst <- toGRanges(wz[,c('name1', 'zstart1', 'end1')])
zst <- toGRanges(wz[,c('name2', 'zstart2', 'end2')])
kpPlotLinks(kp,data=wst,data2=zst,col='darkgrey',r0=0.1)

dev.off()

offseq <- wz[,c('name2', 'zstart2', 'end2')]
of <- subset(offseq,name2!='chr23')
write.table(of, 'chr23-hits.bed', col.names=F, row.names=F, quote=F, sep='\t')
#merge with bedtools...
of2 <- read.table('chr23-hits_merged.bed', header=F)
of2$length <- abs(of2$V3-of2$V2)

```

Pre-Processing

File Paths

Paths to relevant files.

Using crow genome 5.6.

```

#genome-based files
genomedir=/crex/proj/uppstore2019047/Genomes/crow5.6
genome=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.fasta
repeats=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.repeats.bed
chrbed=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.CHRS.bed
chr=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.genome
ctsnp=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.TS_SNPs.bed
allsnp=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.AllSNPs.bed
atacsub=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.SUB.ATACseq.bed

#sequence-based files
rawdata=/crex/proj/uppstore2019047/nobackup/wgbs/corvus/raw

#sample-id list
list=/crex/proj/uppstore2019047/nobackup/wgbs/corvus/lists/All_Samples.list

```

Extract Genome Features

CpG Islands

For our analyses, let's start by making a CpG island track, so we can at least look at CpG islands on top of our gff gene track. I'll do this with HMMs using [makeCGI](#)

```
#!/bin/bash

#SBATCH -A snic2018-3-655
#SBATCH -p core
#SBATCH -n 5
#SBATCH -t 48:00:00

Rscript CGI_SINGLE.R
```

Rscript:

```
library(makeCGI);
.CGIOptions=CGIOptions();
.CGIOptions$rawdat.type="txt";
.CGIOptions$species="Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished";
.CGIOptions;
makeCGI(.CGIOptions);
5000
```

Now output a bed file following strict CpG island definitions, the standard definition is:

- length at least 200
- Percent GC > 50%
- obs/expected CG ratio > 60%

But I will increase our thresholds so that we have higher confidence in our intervals:

- length at least 250
- Percent GC > 60%
- obs/expected CG ratio > 75%

```
awk '($4 > 250) && ($7 > 0.6) && ($8 > 0.75){print $1, $2, $3}' CGI-
Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.txt | sed '1d' | tr ' ' \\t >
../../Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.cgi.bed
```

Which gives us about 18.5K CpG islands:

```
cat Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.cgi.bed | wc -l
18526
```

Repeat Track

Using repeatmasker, I will subset our 5mC into repeat and non-repeat.

```
#!/bin/bash

#SBATCH -A snic2018-3-655
#SBATCH -p core
#SBATCH -n 10
#SBATCH -t 36:00:00

module load RepeatMasker

genomedir=/crex/proj/upstore2019047/Genomes/crow5.6
genome=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.fasta

RepeatMasker ${genome} -species chicken -nolow -pa 10 -gff -dir ${genomedir};
```

And we can use the raw gff file output for masking, or convert it to a standard bed with the following:

```
grep -v '#' Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.fa.out.gff | awk '{OFS="\t"}
{print $1, $4, $5, $7}' > Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.repeats.bed
```

RNAseq Data

Our RNAseq data comes in a format like this:

```
head data_Expression_Liver_Sup59_Sup60.txt
geneID chr geneStart geneEnd PAR tissue sampleID fpkm
LOGfpkm zFPKM KeepActiveAllyN
LOC104683219 chr12 5008410 5014985 0 liver S_Up_60 0 -Inf -
Inf 0
LOC104683285 chr12 9156363 9187251 0 liver S_Up_60 0 -Inf -
Inf 0
```

Switch it to bed:

```
grep -v 'geneID' data_Expression_Liver_Sup59_Sup60.txt | awk '{OFS="\t"}{print
$2, $3, $4, $1, $7, $8, $9, $10}' > RNAseq_Liver.bed

grep -v 'geneID' data_Expression_Spleen_Sup59_Sup60.txt | awk '{OFS="\t"}{print
$2, $3, $4, $1, $7, $8, $9, $10}' > RNAseq_Spleen.bed

#for me, load the R environment on the cluster
conda activate r_env
```

Now within R:

```

library(maditr)
tab <- read.table('RNAseq_Liver.bed')
tab2 <- dcast(tab,V1+V2+V3+V4~V5, value.var=c('V6','V7','V8'))
write.table(tab2,file='RNAseq_Liver_Long.txt',quote=FALSE)

#and spleen
tab <- read.table('RNAseq_Spleen.bed')
tab2 <- dcast(tab,V1+V2+V3+V4~V5, value.var=c('V6','V7','V8'))
write.table(tab2,file='RNAseq_Spleen_Long.txt',quote=FALSE)

```

The columns are now:

```
$chr $start $end $gene $fpkmH59 $fpkmH60 $logfpkmH59 $logfpkmH60 $zfpkmH59 $zfpkmH60
```

```

awk '{FS=" "}{OFS="\t"}{print $2, $3, $4, $5, $6, $7, $8, $9, $10, $11}'
RNAseq_Spleen_Long.txt | grep -v 'V2' > RNAseq_M.bed
awk '{FS=" "}{OFS="\t"}{print $2, $3, $4, $5, $6, $7, $8, $9, $10, $11}'
RNAseq_Liver_Long.txt | grep -v 'V2' > RNAseq_L.bed

#clean up
rm RNAseq_Liver.bed RNAseq_Spleen.bed *_Long.txt

```

ATACseq Data

Our ATACseq data comes in a format like this:

```

head ATACseq.header.txt
(1) MACS-narrow-peak
chr    peak_start    peak_end    sample_ID    integer_score    NA
fold_change    log10Pvalue    log10Qvalue    summit

head ATACseq.master.tab
chr1    3540    5265    F_Sorted_D_Ko_29__Liver__chr1_BAMPE_peak_1    417    .
7.78565    44.93091    41.71688    101
chr1    6230    6418    F_Sorted_D_Ko_29__Liver__chr1_BAMPE_peak_2    24    .
2.29110    4.26820    2.46941    157
chr1    55048    55797    F_Sorted_D_Ko_29__Liver__chr1_BAMPE_peak_3    369    .
9.46569    39.96866    36.95573    122
chr1    65333    66057    F_Sorted_D_Ko_29__Liver__chr1_BAMPE_peak_4    251    .
9.20883    27.79256    25.19434    308
chr1    86099    86474    F_Sorted_D_Ko_29__Liver__chr1_BAMPE_peak_5    64    .
4.83387    8.44325    6.43025    235
chr1    98257    98369    F_Sorted_D_Ko_29__Liver__chr1_BAMPE_peak_6    22    .
2.96774    4.08847    2.29980    5

```

Let's get it into a minimal bed format, our metadata columns are now \$integer_score \$fold_change and \$summit :

```
cat seq_processed_data/gw_MACS_peak_calling/*narrowPeakAll_Norm_bedSorted >
~/ATACseq.master.tab
sed 's/F_Sorted/_F_/g' ATACseq.master.tab | sed 's/M_Sorted/_M_/g' | awk
'BEGIN {FS="__"}{OFS="\t"}{print $1, $2, $3, $4, $5}' | sed 's/Liver/_L_ADL/g' |
sed 's/Spleen/_M_ADL/g' | awk '{OFS="\t"}{print $1, $2, $3, $5$6$4, $8, $10,
$13}' > Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.ATACseq.bed
```

```
head Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.ATACseq.bed
chr1 3540 5265 D_Ko_29_L_ADL_F 417 7.78565 101
chr1 6230 6418 D_Ko_29_L_ADL_F 24 2.29110 157
chr1 55048 55797 D_Ko_29_L_ADL_F 369 9.46569 122
chr1 65333 66057 D_Ko_29_L_ADL_F 251 9.20883 308
chr1 86099 86474 D_Ko_29_L_ADL_F 64 4.83387 235
chr1 98257 98369 D_Ko_29_L_ADL_F 22 2.96774 5
chr1 99108 99366 D_Ko_29_L_ADL_F 120 6.10837 105
chr1 100168 100498 D_Ko_29_L_ADL_F 125 6.18720 138
```

We will keep this whole-sample dataset, but also subset just our samples with WGBS data, since we have quite a few samples here:

```
awk '{print $4}' Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.ATACseq.bed | sort | uniq
-c 72473 D_Ko_29_L_ADL_F 46020 D_Ko_C31_L_ADL_M 63480 D_Ko_C31_M_ADL_M 76289
D_Ko_C36_L_ADL_M 59499 D_Ko_C36_M_ADL_M 63157 D_Ko_C45_L_ADL_F 62383
D_Ko_C45_M_ADL_F 72436 D_Ko_C53_L_ADL_M 70001 D_Ko_C53_M_ADL_M 70271
D_Ko_C59_L_ADL_F 66787 D_Ko_C59_M_ADL_F 105182 D_Ko_C63_L_ADL_M 58792
D_Ko_C63_M_ADL_M 61054 S_Up_59_L_ADL_M 66931 S_Up_59_M_ADL_M 60461
S_Up_60_L_ADL_F 73996 S_Up_60_M_ADL_F 75400 S_Up_65_L_ADL_F 74361
S_Up_65_M_ADL_F 60006 S_Up_69_L_ADL_F 71747 S_Up_69_M_ADL_F 61800
S_Up_71_L_ADL_F 59212 S_Up_71_M_ADL_F 71640 S_Up_75_L_ADL_M 60310
S_Up_75_M_ADL_M 73875 S_Up_87_L_ADL_F 55110 S_Up_87_M_ADL_F 77806
S_Up_91_L_ADL_M 72939 S_Up_91_M_ADL_M
```

Subset the individuals we analyze:

```
uniqsamp=/crex/proj/upstore2019047/nobackup/wgbs/corvus/lists/Unique_Samples.lis
tcat
$uniqsampD_Ko_C31_BL_ADL_MD_Ko_C45_BL_ADL_FS_Up_H32_BL_CHK_MS_Up_H59_BL_ADL_MS_Up
_H59_L_ADL_MS_Up_H59_M_ADL_MS_Up_H60_BL_ADL_FS_Up_H60_L_ADL_FS_Up_H60_M_ADL_Fgrep
-wf $uniqsamp Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.RNaseq.bed >
Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.SUB.RNaseq.bedgrep -wf $uniqsamp
Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.ATACseq.bed >
Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.SUB.ATACseq.bedrnasub=${genomdir}/Corvus_co
rnix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.SUB.RNaseq.bedatacsub=${genomdir}/Corvus_cornix__S_U
p_H32_v5.6_polished.SUB.ATACseq.bed
```

Poolseq SNP Track

We have 99 unique crow sample fragment libraries WGS illumina. From these I subset 2 Gb each from each.

```

reformat.sh t=3 -Xmx15g
in1=/proj/uppstore2017156/b2010059/private/rawdata/POPseq/fastq_illumina_shortRea
ds/DNA_113_pair_1_Illumina_ins_400_RL_100_date_120913_FCID_AD18MTACXX_BC_TTAGGC_1
ibraryfolder_Sample_S09_lane_L006_C.cornix_S_Up_H51_tissue_blood.fq.gz
in2=/proj/uppstore2017156/b2010059/private/rawdata/POPseq/fastq_illumina_shortRea
ds/DNA_113_pair_2_Illumina_ins_400_RL_100_date_120913_FCID_AD18MTACXX_BC_TTAGGC_1
ibraryfolder_Sample_S09_lane_L006_C.cornix_S_Up_H51_tissue_blood.fq.gz
out=/crex/proj/uppstore2019047/nobackup/poolseq/fastq/S_Up_H51.fastq.gz
samplebasestarget=2000000000;

```

This output a few samples with low reads, I removed the 3 individuals below corresponding to 700 Mb of data (n=2) and 1 individual with only 4 Mb. This leaves us with 95 individuals with roughly 2 Gb each, therefore roughly 175x coverage

Output: (47.09%)	20000000 reads (47.09%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (100.00%)	19728298 reads (100.00%)	1972829800 bases
Output: (49.54%)	20000000 reads (49.54%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (93.39%)	20000000 reads (93.39%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (68.68%)	20000000 reads (68.68%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (59.69%)	20000000 reads (59.69%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (72.33%)	20000000 reads (72.33%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (100.00%)	7843674 reads (100.00%)	784367400 bases
Output: (93.89%)	20000000 reads (93.89%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (52.35%)	20000000 reads (52.35%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (33.81%)	20000000 reads (33.81%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (94.49%)	20000000 reads (94.49%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (100.00%)	19622496 reads (100.00%)	1962249600 bases
Output: (78.30%)	20000000 reads (78.30%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (86.16%)	20000000 reads (86.16%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (73.26%)	20000000 reads (73.26%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (66.47%)	20000000 reads (66.47%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (10.03%)	20000000 reads (10.03%)	2000000000 bases
Output:	20000000 reads (8.08%)	2000000000 bases (8.08%)
Output: (11.39%)	20000000 reads (11.39%)	2000000000 bases

Output: (12.84%)	20000000 reads (12.84%)	200000000 bases
Output: (57.94%)	20000000 reads (57.94%)	200000000 bases
Output: (100.00%)	19409732 reads (100.00%)	1940973200 bases
Output: (100.00%)	19508666 reads (100.00%)	1950866600 bases
Output: (97.95%)	20000000 reads (97.95%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (74.38%)	20000000 reads (74.38%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (48.37%)	20000000 reads (48.37%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (100.00%)	19825956 reads (100.00%)	1982595600 bases
Output: (100.00%)	18695728 reads (100.00%)	1869572800 bases
Output: (95.42%)	20000000 reads (95.42%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (100.00%)	16299724 reads (100.00%)	1629972400 bases
Output: (80.68%)	20000000 reads (80.68%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (100.00%)	18941664 reads (100.00%)	1894166400 bases
Output: (46.78%)	20000000 reads (46.78%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (47.61%)	20000000 reads (47.61%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (63.09%)	20000000 reads (63.09%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (100.00%)	18532002 reads (100.00%)	1853200200 bases
Output: (47.00%)	20000000 reads (47.00%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (100.00%)	19048580 reads (100.00%)	1904858000 bases
Output: (66.40%)	20000000 reads (66.40%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (72.34%)	20000000 reads (72.34%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (70.40%)	20000000 reads (70.40%)	2000000000 bases
Output:	43520 reads (100.00%)	4352000 bases (100.00%)
Output: (46.22%)	20000000 reads (46.22%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (98.56%)	20000000 reads (98.56%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (90.70%)	20000000 reads (90.70%)	2000000000 bases
Output: (100.00%)	19096636 reads (100.00%)	1909663600 bases
Output: (100.00%)	18987202 reads (100.00%)	1898720200 bases

Output: (96.23%)	20000000 reads (96.23%)	200000000 bases
Output: (69.26%)	20000000 reads (69.26%)	200000000 bases
Output: (85.61%)	20000000 reads (85.61%)	200000000 bases
Output: (59.42%)	20000000 reads (59.42%)	200000000 bases
Output: (46.46%)	20000000 reads (46.46%)	200000000 bases
Output: (42.96%)	20000000 reads (42.96%)	200000000 bases
Output: (45.61%)	20000000 reads (45.61%)	200000000 bases
Output: (50.32%)	20000000 reads (50.32%)	200000000 bases
Output: (73.70%)	20000000 reads (73.70%)	200000000 bases
Output: (70.91%)	20000000 reads (70.91%)	200000000 bases
Output: (74.15%)	20000000 reads (74.15%)	200000000 bases
Output: (66.61%)	20000000 reads (66.61%)	200000000 bases
Output: (85.06%)	20000000 reads (85.06%)	200000000 bases
Output: (69.83%)	20000000 reads (69.83%)	200000000 bases
Output: (79.70%)	20000000 reads (79.70%)	200000000 bases
Output: (61.13%)	20000000 reads (61.13%)	200000000 bases
Output: (81.72%)	20000000 reads (81.72%)	200000000 bases
Output: (67.21%)	20000000 reads (67.21%)	200000000 bases
Output: (63.50%)	20000000 reads (63.50%)	200000000 bases
Output: (54.48%)	20000000 reads (54.48%)	200000000 bases
Output: (100.00%)	7210798 reads (100.00%)	721079800 bases
Output: (83.90%)	20000000 reads (83.90%)	200000000 bases
Output: (59.57%)	20000000 reads (59.57%)	200000000 bases
Output: (65.61%)	20000000 reads (65.61%)	200000000 bases
Output: (52.11%)	20000000 reads (52.11%)	200000000 bases
Output: (57.05%)	20000000 reads (57.05%)	200000000 bases
Output: (46.07%)	20000000 reads (46.07%)	200000000 bases
Output: (51.83%)	20000000 reads (51.83%)	200000000 bases

Output: (48.60%)	20000000 reads (48.60%)	200000000 bases
Output: (56.12%)	20000000 reads (56.12%)	200000000 bases
Output: (56.32%)	20000000 reads (56.32%)	200000000 bases
Output: (47.98%)	20000000 reads (47.98%)	200000000 bases
Output: (64.47%)	20000000 reads (64.47%)	200000000 bases
Output: (60.98%)	20000000 reads (60.98%)	200000000 bases
Output: (96.61%)	20000000 reads (96.61%)	200000000 bases
Output: (80.60%)	20000000 reads (80.60%)	200000000 bases
Output: (69.67%)	20000000 reads (69.67%)	200000000 bases
Output: (86.51%)	20000000 reads (86.51%)	200000000 bases
Output: (68.42%)	20000000 reads (68.42%)	200000000 bases
Output: (66.56%)	20000000 reads (66.56%)	200000000 bases
Output: (100.00%)	19157704 reads (100.00%)	1915770400 bases
Output: (10.56%)	20000000 reads (10.56%)	200000000 bases
Output: (11.09%)	20000000 reads (11.09%)	200000000 bases
Output: (38.67%)	20100502 reads (38.67%)	1999999949 bases
Output: (51.67%)	20100502 reads (51.67%)	1999999949 bases
Output: (34.23%)	20100502 reads (34.23%)	1999999949 bases
Output: (44.21%)	20100502 reads (44.21%)	1999999949 bases
Output: (48.85%)	20100502 reads (48.85%)	1999999949 bases
Output: (11.97%)	20000000 reads (11.97%)	200000000 bases
Output: (11.31%)	20000000 reads (11.31%)	200000000 bases

Per sample output:

```
setwd("E:/Research/scratch/crow_epidiv/poolseq/")output <-
read.table("per_sample_gb.txt",header=TRUE)head(output)library(ggplot2)library(vi
ridis)ggplot(output, aes(x=Sample,y=Gb))+
geom_bar(stat="identity",fill=viridis(1))+ theme_minimal(base_size=18)+
theme(axis.text.x=element_text(angle=90,vjust=.45,hjust=1))
```


The 3 samples with primarily low Gb were removed.

Map with bwa:

```
#!/bin/bash#SBATCH -A snic2018-3-655#SBATCH -p node#SBATCH -n 1#SBATCH -t
48:00:00wd=/crex/proj/uppstore2019047/nobackup/poolseq/bamsreads=/crex/proj/uppstore2019047/nobackup/poolseq/fastq/Master_Crow.fastq.gzgenome=/crex/proj/uppstore2019047/Genomes/crow5.6/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.fasta#Pseudo Read
group      ID=Crow_Poolseq      PU=Crow_Poolseq      SM=Crow_Poolseq
LB=Crow_Poolseq#Index genomebwa index ${genome}#Mapping, subset only mapped reads
that pass base QC      bwa mem -M -p -t 20 -R
"@RG\tID:${ID}\tSM:${SM}\tPL:ILLUMINA\tPU:${PU}\tLB:${LB}" ${genome} ${reads} |
samtools sort -@20 -o ${wd}/Crow_Master.bam -;      samtools view -b -f 3 -F
524 ${wd}/Crow_Master.bam > ${wd}/Crow_Master.map.bam      samtools index -b
${wd}/Crow_Master.map.bam;      rm ${wd}/Crow_Master.bam      gatk
MarkDuplicates -I ${wd}/Crow_Master.map.bam -O ${wd}/Crow_Master.dedup.bam --
CREATE_INDEX true --REMOVE_DUPLICATES true --MAX_RECORDS_IN_RAM 2000000
```

Call variants with the pooled data, submit job per chromosome (only analyzing chromosomes, not scaffolds). First create a sequence dictionary:

```
gatk CreateSequenceDictionary -R ${genome} -O ${genome}.dict
```

```
#!/bin/bash#SBATCH -A snic2018-3-655#SBATCH -p core#SBATCH -n 1#SBATCH -t
36:00:00outdir=/crex/proj/uppstore2019047/nobackup/poolseq/vcfgenome=/crex/proj/uppstore2019047/Genomes/crow5.6/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.fastabamfile
=/crex/proj/uppstore2019047/nobackup/poolseq/bams/Crow_Master.dedup.bamchr=${1}gatk HaplotypeCaller -R ${genome} -L ${chr} --native-pair-hmm-threads 2 -I
${bamfile} -O ${outdir}/${chr}.vcf.gz -ploidy 2 -ERC GVCF --output-mode
EMIT_VARIANTS_ONLY
```

And submit per chromosome:

```
for scaf in $(awk '{print $1}'
/crex/proj/uppstore2019047/Genomes/crow5.6/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.
CHRS.bed); do sbatch HC_poolseq.sh ${scaf}; done
```

Genotype all chromosomes:

```
#!/bin/bash#SBATCH -A snic2018-3-655#SBATCH -p core#SBATCH -n 1#SBATCH -t
6:00:00outdir=/crex/proj/uppstore2019047/nobackup/poolseq/vcfgenome=/crex/proj/up
pstore2019047/Genomes/crow5.6/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.fastachr=${1}
gatk GenotypeGVCFs -R ${genome} -L ${chr} -v ${outdir}/${chr}.vcf.gz -O
${outdir}/${chr}.RAW.vcf.gz -new-qual -ploidy 2
```

And submit...

```
for scaf in $(awk '{print $1}'
/crex/proj/uppstore2019047/Genomes/crow5.6/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.
CHRS.bed); do sbatch Genotype.sh ${scaf}; done
```

Gather all the chromosome-level vcfs:

```
#!/bin/bash#SBATCH -A snic2018-3-655#SBATCH -p core#SBATCH -n 5#SBATCH -t
24:00:00genome=/crex/proj/uppstore2019047/Genomes/crow5.6/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32
_v5.6_polished.fastamkdir vcf/rawmv vcf/chr* vcf/raw#merge vcfsbcftools concat
vcf/raw/*.RAW.vcf.gz -Oz -o vcf/Master_Crow.vcf.gztabix
vcf/Master_Crow.vcf.gz#Subset SNPs and Indels for variant callinggatk
SelectVariants -V vcf/Master_Crow.vcf.gz -select-type SNP -O
vcf/Master_Crow.RAW.SNP.vcf.gzgatk SelectVariants -V vcf/Master_Crow.vcf.gz -
select-type INDEL -O vcf/Master_Crow.RAW.INDEL.vcf.gz#SNPS variant qualitygatk
VariantsToTable \-R ${genome} \-V vcf/Master_Crow.RAW.SNP.vcf.gz \-F CHROM -F POS
-F QUAL -F QD -F DP -F MQ -F MQRankSum -F FS -F ReadPosRankSum -F SOR \-GF DP \-O
vcf/Master_Crow.RAW.SNP.table#INDELS variant qualitygatk VariantsToTable \-R
${genome} \-V vcf/Master_Crow.RAW.INDEL.vcf.gz \-F CHROM -F POS -F QUAL -F QD -F
DP -F MQ -F MQRankSum -F FS -F ReadPosRankSum -F SOR \-GF DP \-O
vcf/Master_Crow.RAW.INDEL.tableRscript Plot_VarQuality.R
```

And the Rscript...

```
library('gridExtra')library('ggplot2')library('reshape')VCFsnps <-
read.csv('vcf/Master_Crow.RAW.SNP.table', header = T, na.strings=c("", "NA"), sep
= "\t")VCFindel <- read.csv('vcf/Master_Crow.RAW.INDEL.table', header = T,
na.strings=c("", "NA"), sep = "\t")dim(VCFsnps)dim(VCFindel)VCF <- rbind(VCFsnps,
VCFindel)VCF$Variant <- factor(c(rep("SNPs", dim(VCFsnps)[1]), rep("Indels",
dim(VCFindel)[1])))snps <- '#A9E2E4'indels <- '#F4CCCA'#Depends on datasetDP <-
ggplot(VCF, aes(x=DP, fill=variant)) + geom_density(alpha=0.3) +
coord_cartesian(xlim=c(0,2000))QD <- ggplot(VCF, aes(x=QD, fill=variant)) +
geom_density(alpha=.3) + coord_cartesian(xlim=c(0,40))FS <- ggplot(VCF,
aes(x=FS, fill=variant)) + geom_density(alpha=.3) + ylim(0,0.1)+
coord_cartesian(xlim=c(0,100))MQ <- ggplot(VCF, aes(x=MQ, fill=variant)) +
geom_density(alpha=.3) + coord_cartesian(xlim=c(20,60))MQRankSum <- ggplot(VCF,
aes(x=MQRankSum, fill=variant)) + geom_density(alpha=.3) +
coord_cartesian(xlim=c(-15,5))SOR <- ggplot(VCF, aes(x=SOR, fill=variant)) +
geom_density(alpha=.3) + coord_cartesian(xlim=c(0,10))ReadPosRankSum <-
ggplot(VCF, aes(x=ReadPosRankSum, fill=variant)) + geom_density(alpha=.3) +
geom_vline(xintercept=c(-10,10,-20,20), size=1, colour =
c(snps,snps,indels,indels)) +
coord_cartesian(xlim=c(-10,10))svg("GW_PopLevel.svg", height=20,
width=15)theme_set(theme_classic(base_size = 18))grid.arrange(QD, DP, FS, MQ,
MQRankSum, SOR, ReadPosRankSum, nrow=4)dev.off()
```


Filter for sites, really I'm most concerned with DP here. I want at least 20 of the individuals to have a site to keep it, so therefore we want at least 20X coverage, and I also don't want repeats, so I'll remove any sites where we have theoretically higher than 3x coverage per sample (300x).

```
#!/bin/bash#SBATCH -A snic2018-3-655#SBATCH -p core#SBATCH -n 1#SBATCH -t
6:00:00outdir=/crex/proj/upstore2019047/nobackup/poolseq/vcfgenome=/crex/proj/up
pstore2019047/Genomes/crow5.6/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.fastamodule
load GATK/4.1.4.1#Hard Filteringgatk VariantFiltration \-V
vcf/Master_Crow.RAW.SNP.vcf.gz -filter "QD < 3.0" --filter-name "QD3" \-filter
"SOR > 3.0" --filter-name "SOR3" \-filter "DP < 20.0" --filter-name "DP20" \-
filter "DP > 300.0" --filter-name "DP300" \-filter "FS > 60.0" --filter-name
"FS60" \-filter "MQ < 30.0" --filter-name "MQ30" \-o
vcf/Master_Crow.SNP.vcf.gz#Set the filtered genotypes to no call, counting these
variants will tell you samples filtered at the population-level gatk
SelectVariants -V vcf/Master_Crow.SNP.vcf.gz --exclude-filtered --set-filtered-
gt-to-nocall --remove-unused-alternates -o vcf/Master_Crow.SNP.filt.vcf.gz
```

And convert this filtered vcf to bed:

```
zcat Master_Crow.SNP.filt.vcf.gz | awk 'BEGIN{OFS="\t"}{print $1, $2-1, $2, $4, $5}' | grep -v '#' > Master_Crow_AllSnps.bedhead Master_Crow_AllSnps.bedchr10
760    761    T        Cchr10  1159    1160    A        Cchr10  1252    1253
T      Cchr10  1287    1288    G        Achr10  1336    1337    C        G
```

Now subset just the C-T SNPs:

```
awk '((($4 == "c" && $5 == "T") || ($4 == "T" && $5 == "c")) || $0 ~ /^#/ )'
Master_Crow_AllSnps.bed | awk '{OFS="\t"}{print $1, $2, $3}' >
Master_Crow_CT_SNPs.bed
```

Which gives us about 900K C-T snps that should be considered for the bisulfite experiment.

```
cat Master_Crow_CT_SNPs.bed | wc -l898356
```

Overview: Files

An overview of our track-based files:

- Genome file
- Repeats .bed
- RNAseq Zfpkm values
- ATACseq fold change & peak heights
- PoolSeq SNP and C-T (AND A-G for reverse strand) SNP file for masking

Trim to Extract

Script that will take raw fastq data and then trim, map, deduplication, extract, and mask 5mC:

Prepare genome for mapping:

```
#!/bin/bash

#SBATCH --get-user-env
#SBATCH --mail-user=merondun@bio.1mu.de
#SBATCH --clusters=biohpc_gen
#SBATCH --partition=biohpc_gen_normal
#SBATCH --cpus-per-task=15
#SBATCH --mem-per-cpu=4763mb
#SBATCH --time=48:00:00

#genome-based files
genomedir=/dss/dss1egfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-
0018/projects/2021__HybridZone_Epigenetics/Genomes/Corvus_5.6
genome=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.fasta
cgi=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.cgi.bed
repeats=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.repeats.bed
annotation=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.annotation.bed
rnaseq=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.RNAseq.bed
atacseq=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.ATACseq.bed
rnasub=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.SUB.RNAseq.bed
atacsub=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.SUB.ATACseq.bed
```

```

chrbed=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.CHRS.bed
chr=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.genome
ctsnp=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.CTSNPs.bed
allsnp=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.AllSNPs.bed

#sequence-based files
rawdata=/crex/proj/uppstore2019047/nobackup/wgbs/corvus/raw

#sample-id list
list=/crex/proj/uppstore2019047/nobackup/wgbs/corvus/lists/All_Samples.list

bismark_genome_preparation ${genomedir}

```

And the full pipeline:

```

#!/bin/bash

#SBATCH --get-user-env
#SBATCH --mail-user=merondun@bio.lmu.de
#SBATCH --clusters=biohpc_gen
#SBATCH --partition=biohpc_gen_normal
#SBATCH --cpus-per-task=15
#SBATCH --mem-per-cpu=4763mb
#SBATCH --time=48:00:00

SCRATCH=tmp/$SLURM_JOB_ID
mkdir tmp
mkdir $SCRATCH

#genome-based files
genomedir=/dss/dsslegfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-0018/projects/2021__HybridZone_Epigenetics/Genomes/Corvus_5.6
genome=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.fasta
cgi=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.cgi.bed
chrbed=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.CHRS.bed
chr=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.genome
ctsnp=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.TS_SNPs.bed
repeats=${genomedir}/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.repeats.bed

#working directories
rawdata=/dss/dsslegfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-0018/rawdata/Bisulfite-Seq/WGBS
basedir=/dss/dsslegfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-0018/projects/2021__HybridZone_Epigenetics/ATACseq_Methylation_Analyses/2021_NOV/Clip_9_Q20
workdir=${basedir}/scratch
outdir=${basedir}/5mC_raw

mkdir ${basedir}
mkdir ${workdir}
mkdir ${outdir}
mkdir ${outdir}/fastqc

RUN=$1

#cat ${rawdata}/${RUN}*_R1__*.fastq.gz > $SCRATCH/${RUN}.R1.fastq.gz

```

```

#cat ${rawdata}/${RUN}*__R2__*fastq.gz > $SCRATCH/${RUN}.R2.fastq.gz

cd ${workdir}

#Trim adapters
#trim_galore --fastqc -j 10 --clip_r1 9 --clip_r2 9 --paired --quality 20 --
output_dir ${workdir} ${SCRATCH}/${RUN}.R1.fastq.gz ${SCRATCH}/${RUN}.R2.fastq.gz

#Re-run fastqc on final cleaned data
#fastqc -t 8 ${workdir}/${RUN}*_val*.fq.gz

#mv ${workdir}/${RUN}*cleaned_fastqc.* ${outdir}/fastqc

#Map reads
bismark --parallel 7 --output_dir ${workdir} --genome ${genomedir} -1
${workdir}/${RUN}.R1_val_1.fq.gz -2 ${workdir}/${RUN}.R2_val_2.fq.gz

#Deduplicate
deduplicate_bismark --paired ${workdir}/${RUN}.R1_val_1_bismark_bt2_pe.bam --
output_dir ${workdir}

#Extract methylation
bismark_methylation_extractor --parallel 10 --gzip --bedgraph --ignore_3prime_r2
1 --ignore_r2 3 --buffer_size 60G --cytosine_report --genome_folder ${genomedir}
--output ${workdir} ${workdir}/${RUN}.R1_val_1_bismark_bt2_pe.deduplicated.bam

#Remove any positions overlapping a transition
bedtools subtract -A -a ${workdir}/${RUN}.*bismark.cov.gz -b ${ctsnp} >
${workdir}/${RUN}.filt_cutsite_ctsnp.tmp

#Only keep sites on the major chromosomes
bedtools intersect -wb -a ${chrsbed} -b ${workdir}/${RUN}.filt_cutsite_ctsnp.tmp
| awk '{OFS="\t"}{print $4, $5, $6, $7, $8, $9}' | sort | uniq >
${workdir}/${RUN}.filt_cutsite_ctsnp_chrs.tmp

#Divide files further into repeat-region 5mC, and then our final 5mC positions
for analysis
bedtools intersect -wb -a ${repeats} -b
${workdir}/${RUN}.filt_cutsite_ctsnp_chrs.tmp | awk '{OFS="\t"}{print $5, $6, $7,
$8, $9, $10}' | sort | uniq | bgzip -c > ${outdir}/${RUN}.CpG_in_Repeats.cov.gz

#Subtract repeats
bedtools subtract -A -a ${workdir}/${RUN}.filt_cutsite_ctsnp_chrs.tmp -b
${repeats} | bgzip -c > ${outdir}/${RUN}.CpG_5mC.cov.gz

### Count methylation calls between raw and filtered sets
mkdir $basedir/counts

#make a file with the first 2 columns
echo -e "${RUN}\n${RUN}\n${RUN}\n${RUN}\n${RUN}" > $basedir/counts/${RUN}.sample
echo -e "RAW\nTSSNP\nChr\nRepeatless\nRepeats" > $basedir/counts/${RUN}.field

#now for the counts
zcat $basedir/scratch/${RUN}.*bismark.cov.gz | wc -l >
$basedir/counts/${RUN}.counts

```

```

cat $basedir/scratch/${RUN}.filt_cutsite_ctsnp.tmp | wc -l >>
$basedir/counts/${RUN}.counts
cat $basedir/scratch/${RUN}.filt_cutsite_ctsnp_chrs.tmp | wc -l >>
$basedir/counts/${RUN}.counts
zcat $basedir/5mC_raw/${RUN}.CpG_5mC.cov.gz | wc -l >>
$basedir/counts/${RUN}.counts
zcat $basedir/5mC_raw/${RUN}.CpG_in_Repeats.cov.gz | wc -l >>
$basedir/counts/${RUN}.counts

paste $basedir/counts/${RUN}.sample $basedir/counts/${RUN}.field
$basedir/counts/${RUN}.counts > $basedir/counts/${RUN}.count

```

And submit a bash script for each sample:

```

for i in $(cat Samples.list); do sbatch -J WGBS_${i} Call_Methylation_WGBS.sh
${i}; done

```

CpG Summary

I'll make an R input file from the CpG summary, and will also plot the methylation bias (M-Bias) plots here. But first, let's get a count for the raw methylation calls for each sample, as well as how many were removed for each filter.

```

mkdir counts
echo -e "Sample\tFilter\tCount" > counts/header.txt

for i in $(cat Samples.list); do

#make a file with the first 2 columns
echo -e "${i}\n${i}\n${i}\n${i}\n${i}" > counts/${i}.sample
echo -e "RAW\nTsSNP\nChr\nRepeatless\nRepeats" > counts/${i}.field

#now for the counts
zcat scratch/${i}.*bismark.cov.gz | wc -l > counts/${i}.counts
cat scratch/${i}.filt_cutsite_ctsnp.tmp | wc -l >> counts/${i}.counts
cat scratch/${i}.filt_cutsite_ctsnp_chrs.tmp | wc -l >> counts/${i}.counts
zcat 5mC_raw/${i}.CpG_5mC.cov.gz | wc -l >> counts/${i}.counts
zcat 5mC_raw/${i}.CpG_in_Repeats.cov.gz | wc -l >> counts/${i}.counts

paste counts/${i}.sample counts/${i}.field counts/${i}.counts > counts/${i}.count

done
cat counts/header.txt counts/*.count > 5mC_Counts.txt
rm -rf counts

```

And for the M-Bias plots, I first merge them together and add a sample field, and then I manicure them in excel because they are in a terrible format:

```

for RUN in $(ls *M-bias.txt | sed 's/\.*//g' ); do

sed -n '/CHG context (R1)/q;p' ${RUN}.*M-bias.txt | egrep -v 'methyl|=|context' \
| grep . | awk -v s=${RUN} '{OFS="\t"}{print s,$0,"R1","CpG"}' >
${RUN}.MBIAS1.tmp

sed -n '/CpG context (R2)/,$p' ${RUN}.*M-bias.txt | sed -n '/CHG context
(R2)/q;p' | egrep -v 'methyl|=|context' \
| grep . | awk -v s=${RUN} '{OFS="\t"}{print s,$0,"R2","CpG"}' >
${RUN}.MBIAS2.tmp

cat ${RUN}.MBIAS1.tmp ${RUN}.MBIAS2.tmp > ${RUN}.M-Bias.txt
rm ${RUN}*MBI*.tmp
done

```

And within R:

```

#Plot methylation value along read lengths
setwd('F:/Research/scratch/crow_atac/2021-11/QC')
library(ggplot2)
library(gridExtra)
library(ggsci)
library(viridis)

wgbs <- read.table('Master.ATAC.MBias.Nov.txt',header=F)
names(wgbs) <-
c('Sample','Position','CountM','CountU','Methylated','Coverage','Read','Context')
wgbs$Experiment <- 'WGBS'
wgbs <- wgbs %>% mutate(Batch = ifelse(grep1('-NO',Sample) ==
T,'Novogene','SciLife'))

bias <- wgbs
bias <- rbind(wgbs,cg1,cgsub,hz1,hz2)

a <- ggplot(bias,aes(x=Position,col=Sample))+
  geom_line(aes(y=Methylated),stat="identity",show.legend=T,size=2)+ylab('Percent
Methylation')+
  theme_classic(base_size=16)+facet_grid(Experiment~Read)+
  scale_color_viridis(discrete=T,option='plasma')+
  coord_cartesian(ylim=c(0,100))
a

#save
png('M_Bias-WGBS-ATAC.png',height=4,width=10,bg='transparent',units='in',res=600)
a
dev.off()

### and counts
library(viridis)
cwgbs <- read.table('Master.ATAC.Counts.Nov.txt',header=F)
names(cwgbs) <- c('Sample','Filter','Count')
cwgbs$Experiment <- 'WGBS'
mdat <- cwgbs

```

```

head(mdat)
mdat$Filter <-
factor(mdat$Filter,levels=c('RAW', 'TsSNP', 'Chr', 'Repeatless', 'Repeats'))
mdat <- mdat %>% mutate(Filter = gsub('RAW', 'Raw CpGs', Filter),
                        Filter = gsub('TsSNP', 'Transition Filter', Filter),
                        Filter = gsub('Chr', 'within Named Chromosomes', Filter))

mdat$label <- round(mdat$Count/1000000,1)
mdat <- subset(mdat, Filter != 'Repeatless' & Filter != 'Repeats')
c <- ggplot(mdat, aes(x=Sample, y=label, fill=Filter, label=label))+
  scale_fill_manual(values=viridis(5))+

  geom_bar(stat='identity', position=position_dodge(width=1))+theme_classic(base_si
ze=16)+
  theme(axis.text.x=element_text(angle=45, vjust=1, hjust=1))+xlab('')+ylab('')
c

png("Counts_AllExperiments.png", height=5,
width=10, bg='transparent', res=600, units='in')
grid.arrange(c)
dev.off()

```

Coverage

```

source('~/.R_Functions.R')
setwd('~/.files')
#### MANHATTAN Genome-wide
#setwd('/dss/dsslegfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-
0018/projects/2021__HybridZone_Epigenetics/ATACseq_Methylation_Analyses/2021_NOV/
Clip_9_Q20/5mC_raw')

library(dplyr)
library(karyoploteR)
library(tidyr)
library(maditr)
library(viridis)
library(LICORS)
library(ggplot2)
library(scales)
library(forcats)

#init legwork
class <- read.table('MasterCoverage-ATAC.bed', header=TRUE)
class <- read.table('WGBS-HZ-Coverage.bed', header=TRUE)
class <- read.table('Master-HZ-RRBS.coverage', header=F)
names(class) <- c('CHR', 'START', 'END', 'value', 'variable')
cm <- melt(class, id.vars=c('CHR', 'START', 'END'))
cm <- cm %>% mutate(Color =ifelse(value >= 50, 'firebrick',
                                ifelse(value >= 25 & value < 50, 'orangered',
                                ifelse(value >= 5 & value < 25,
'orange',
                                ifelse(value >= 2 & value <
5, 'grey30',
                                ifelse(value < 2,
'black', 'yellow'))))))))

```

```

Colors <- c('black','grey30','orange','orangered','firebrick')
Text <- c('<= 2','2 to 5','5 to 25','25 to 50','>= 50')
leg <- data.frame(Colors,Text)

#Set up genome
genome <- read.table('genome5.7.bed',header=FALSE)
genome$start <- 1
genome <- genome[!grep('scaff',genome$V1),]
genome$lab <- gsub('chr',' ',genome$V1)
genome$lab <- gsub('A',' ',genome$lab)
genome$lab <- gsub('Z','100',genome$lab)
genome <- genome %>% arrange(as.integer(lab))
crowG <- makeGRangesFromDataFrame(genome,seqnames.field = 'V1',start.field =
'start',end.field = 'V2')
genome <- read.table('genome5.7.bed',header=FALSE)
genome$start <- 1
genome <- genome[grep('chr23$|chrZ',genome$V1),]
crowG <- makeGRangesFromDataFrame(genome,seqnames.field = 'V1',start.field =
'start',end.field = 'V2')

#Set up genome, only chr Z
genome <- read.table('genome5.6.bed',header=FALSE)
genome <- genome[grep('chr23$|chrZ',genome$V1),]
genome$start <- 1
crowG <- makeGRangesFromDataFrame(genome,seqnames.field = 'V1',start.field =
'start',end.field = 'V2')

#Set up genome, only chr Z
genome <- read.table('genome5.6.bed',header=FALSE)
genome$start <- 1
genome <- genome[!grep('scaff',genome$V1),]
genome$lab <- gsub('chr',' ',genome$V1)
genome$lab <- gsub('A',' ',genome$lab)
genome$lab <- gsub('Z','100',genome$lab)
genome <- genome %>% arrange(as.integer(lab))
crowG <- makeGRangesFromDataFrame(genome,seqnames.field = 'V1',start.field =
'start',end.field = 'V2')

##### PLOT: Manhattan, will require commenting out depending on what you want..
#####
png('Chr23-Z-Coverage_5.7.png',height=6,width=10,units='in',res=600,bg =
"transparent")
png('WG-Coverage_5.7.png',height=6,width=10,units='in',res=600,bg =
"transparent")
#Plot Base
pp <- getDefaultPlotParams(plot.type=4)
pp$leftmargin <- 0.15
kp <- plotKaryotype(plot.type=4, genome = crowG,plot.params = pp)
kpAddBaseNumbers(kp,tick.dist = 1000000,cex=0.5)

#if you need the legend
#legend(x =
"top",inset=c(0,-.1),xpd=TRUE,pch=15,legend=leg$Text,col=leg$Colors,ncol=4,cex=1)

tracks <- length(unique(cm$variable))

```

```

counter <- 0
for (ind in unique(cm$variable)){
  counter <- counter+1
  cat('Current Autotrack: ',counter,' for ',ind,'\n')
  at <- autotrack(current.track = counter, total.tracks = tracks);
  dat <- subset(cm,variable==ind)
  kpRect(kp,chr=dat$CHR,x0=dat$START,x1=dat$END,y0=0,y1=1,r0=at$r0,
r1=at$r1,ymin=0,ymax=1,border=dat$Color,col=dat$Color);
  kpAddLabels(kp,cex=0.65,labels = ind,r0=at$r0, r1=at$r1,col="black",srt=0)
}

dev.off()

```

Analyses

Blast Chicken MHM

Download fasta from Sun 2019 MHM paper:

```

#Location of Genome
genome=/dss/dsslegfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-
0018/projects/2021__HybridZone_Epigenetics/Genomes/Corvus_5.6/Corvus_cornix__S_Up
_H32_v5.6_polished.fasta
#Location of TARGET
mhm=/dss/dsslegfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-
0018/projects/2021__HybridZone_Epigenetics/ATACseq_Methylation_Analyses/2021_NOV/
Clip_9_Q20/MHM_Sequences.fa
#Location of your desired blastDB (directory must be created)
bdb=/dss/dsslegfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-
0021/projects/2021__Cuckoo_Resequencing/modules/blastdb/Corvus5.6

echo "$(tput setaf 1) $(tput setab 7) Creating Blast DB...$(tput sgr 0)"
makeblastdb -in $genome -parse_seqids -dbtype nucl -title corvus5.6 -out $bdb

echo "$(tput setaf 1) $(tput setab 7) Blast away...$(tput sgr 0)"
blastn -query $mhm -db $bdb \
  -outfmt '6 qseqid sseqid pident length mismatch gapopen qstart qend sstart
send evalue bitscore sstrand' \
  -out target.blast

#create header
echo 'qseqid sseqid pident length mismatch gapopen qstart qend sstart send evalue
bitscore sstrand' | tr ' ' '\t' > target.head
cat target.head target.blast > MHMchicken_5.6corvus.blast

#qseqid                sseqid  pident  length  mismatch  gapopen  qstart  qend  sstart  send  evalue  bitscore  sstrand
MHM1_27.140_27.177Mb_2780bp_unit_13_times chr2    81.013  79      11        3        2356   2434   1.48E+08  1.48E+08  2.13E-06  60.2     plus
MHM1_27.237_27.270Mb_2781bp_unit_12_times chr2    81.013  79      11        3        761    839    1.47E+08  1.47E+08  2.14E-06  60.2     minus

```

qseqid	sseqid	pident	length	mismatch	gapopen	qstart	qend	sstart	send	evalue	bitscore	sstrand
MHM1_27.140_27.177Mb_2780bp_unit_13_times	chr2	81.013	79	11	3	2356	2434	1.48E+08	1.48E+08	2.13E-06	60.2	plus

qseqid	sseqid	pident	length	mismatch	gapopen	qstart	qend	sstart	send	evalue	bitscore	sstrand
MHM1_27.237_27.270Mb_2781bp_unit_12_times	chr2	81.013	79	11	3	761	839	1.48E+08	1.48E+08	2.14E-06	60.2	minus

Extract 5mC Data

```
#!/bin/bash

#SBATCH --get-user-env
#SBATCH --mail-user=merondun@bio.lmu.de
#SBATCH --clusters=cm2_tiny
#SBATCH --partition=cm2_tiny
#SBATCH --cpus-per-task=1
#SBATCH --time=6:00:00

#grab only transcripts, not only exons
grep 'transcript' Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.annotation.bed >
tmp/transcripts.bed

for i in $(cat Genes.names); do

#grab each gene individually from the annotation file, output only $chr $start
$end $gene
grep -w $i tmp/transcripts.bed | bedtools sort -i - | bedtools merge -i - -c 6 -o
distinct > tmp/gene.$i.bed

done
```

And then overlap with 5mC data:

```
#!/bin/bash

#SBATCH --get-user-env
#SBATCH --mail-user=merondun@bio.lmu.de
#SBATCH --clusters=cm2_tiny
#SBATCH --partition=cm2_tiny
#SBATCH --cpus-per-task=1
#SBATCH --time=6:00:00

genomedir=/dss/dsslegfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-
0018/projects/2021__HybridZone_Epigenetics/Genomes/Corvus_5.6
genes=$genomedir/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.UniqueTranscripts.bed
cgis=$genomedir/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.cgi.bed
chrs=$genomedir/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.CHRS.bed

for samp in $(cat Samples.list); do

#overlap 5mC positions with data, and then also with CpG islands:
$chr $pos $pos $mCG $countMETH $countUNMETH $genestart $geneend $gene $cgi
zcat $samp.CpG_5mC.cov.gz | \
    bedtools intersect -a - -b $genes -loj | \
    bedtools intersect -a - -b $cgis -loj | \
    bedtools intersect -a - -b $chrs -loj | \
    awk '{OFS="\t"}{print $1, $2, $3, $4, $5, $6, $10,$9-$8, $14, $13-$12,
$17-$16}' | \
    bgzip -c > $samp.bed.gz
```



```

ma = sum(V6)+sum(V5))

names(tab4) <-
c('ID', 'length', 'chr', paste0('mCG.', name), paste0('mC.', name), paste0('mCA.', name))
;
tab4 <- tab4 %>% mutate(AvZ = ifelse(chr == 'chrZ', 'chrZ', 'Autosome'));
tab4$Subanalysis <- 'cgi'

#merge them
tab5 <- rbind(tab2, tab3, tab4)
cat('Saved to variable: ', name, '\n')
#assign it to a new variable
assign(paste0(name), tab5)
#add this sample to our total list
allnames <- unique(c(allnames, name))
}

#get names
vars <- mget(allnames)
# merge the points, keeping all
masterWGBS <- Reduce(function(x, y) merge(x = x, y = y,
by=c('ID', 'length', 'AvZ', 'chr', 'Subanalysis'), all=TRUE), vars)

write.table(masterWGBS, file='Step1.txt', quote=F, sep='\t', row.names=F)

#filter according to missingness, retain sites with no missing data, according to
tissue
samps <- c('S_Up_H60_L_ADL_F', 'S_Up_H60_M_ADL_F',
           'S_Up_H59_L_ADL_M', 'S_Up_H59_M_ADL_M',
           'D_Ko_C45_M_ADL_F', 'D_Ko_C45_L_ADL_F',
           'D_Ko_C31_M_ADL_M', 'D_Ko_C31_L_ADL_M')

sampM <- samps[grepl('_M_AD', samps)]
#remove sites with missing data specific by tissue
covM <- masterWGBS[rowSums(is.na(masterWGBS[grepl('^mCG..*_M_ADL',
names(masterWGBS))])) == 0, ]
#convert to long form
mdat <- NULL
for (samp in sampM) {
  cat('Subsetting: ', samp, '\n')
  v1 <- covM[grepl(paste0('ID|length|AvZ|chr|Subanalysis|', samp), names(covM))]
  v1$Sample <- samp
  names(v1) <- gsub(paste0('.', samp), '', names(v1))
  sex <- ifelse(grepl('ADL_F', samp) == TRUE, 'F', 'M')
  v1$Sex <- sex
  mdat <- rbind(mdat, v1)
}
mdat$Tissue <- 'Spleen'

#and liver
sampL <- samps[grepl('_L_AD', samps)]
#remove sites with missing data specific by tissue
covL <- masterWGBS[rowSums(is.na(masterWGBS[grepl('^mCG..*_L_ADL',
names(masterWGBS))])) == 0, ]
#convert to long form
ldat <- NULL
for (samp in sampL) {

```

```

cat('Subsetting: ', samp, '\n')
v1 <- covL[grepl(paste0('ID|length|AvZ|chr|Subanalysis|', samp), names(covL))]
v1$Sample <- samp
names(v1) <- gsub(paste0('.', samp), '', names(v1))
sex <- ifelse(grepl('ADL_F', samp) == TRUE, 'F', 'M')
v1$Sex <- sex
ldat <- rbind(ldat, v1)
}
ldat$Tissue <- 'Liver'

#merge
cdat <- rbind(mdat, ldat)
cdat$Sample <- gsub('_M_ADL_M', '', cdat$Sample)
cdat$Sample <- gsub('_L_ADL_M', '', cdat$Sample)
cdat$Sample <- gsub('_M_ADL_F', '', cdat$Sample)
cdat$Sample <- gsub('_L_ADL_F', '', cdat$Sample)

write.table(cdat, file='mCG-10x_LongForm_ATAC-
22May9.txt', quote=F, sep='\t', row.names=F)

```

Distribution Summaries

```

setwd('F:/Research/scratch/crow_atac/2021-11/Ratios')
library(dplyr)
library(tidyr)
library(ggplot2)

### Begin with 5mC data
mfmeth <- read.table('mCG-10x_LongForm_ATAC-21Dec21.txt', header=TRUE)
head(mfmeth)
mfmeth <- mfmeth %>% mutate(Subanalysis = gsub('cgi', 'CpG Islands', Subanalysis),
                           Subanalysis = gsub('chromosome', 'whole
Chromosome', Subanalysis),
                           Subanalysis = gsub('gene', 'Genes', Subanalysis),
                           Sex = gsub('F', 'Female', Sex),
                           Sex = gsub('M', 'Male', Sex))

mp2 <- ggplot(mfmeth %>% subset(Subanalysis != 'whole Chromosome'),
              aes(x=mCG, fill=AvZ))+

  geom_histogram(bins=50, show.legend=T, position='identity', alpha=0.6)+ggtitle('Raw
5mC Distributions')+
  facet_grid(Subanalysis+AvZ~Tissue+Sex, scales = 'free')+
  scale_fill_manual(values=c('steelblue1', 'tan'))+xlab('% 5mC')+ylab('Count')+
  theme_classic(base_size=15)
mp2

png('Raw_5mC_Distributions.png', units='in', res=300, height=7, width=11)
mp2
dev.off()

#and just do some sanity checks on raw distributions
d <- read.table('mCG-10x_LongForm_ATAC-21Dec21.txt', header=T)

```

```

d1 <- d %>% group_by(ID,chr,AvZ,Subanalysis,Sex,Tissue) %>% summarize(mc =
mean(mCG))
#and also add start/end
co <- read.table('Gene_CGI_Chrom.coordinates',header=T)
d2 <- merge(d1,co,by=Reduce(intersect, list(names(d1),names(co)))) %>% select(-
c(end,length))
d2$mc <- round(d2$mc,2)
d2$mc[d2$mc==0] <- .01
d3 <- d2 %>% group_by(ID,chr,start,Subanalysis,Tissue,AvZ) %>%
summarize(fmRraw=log2(mc[Sex=='F']/mc[Sex=='M']),

fmSraw=mc[Sex=='F']-mc[Sex=='M'])
d4 <- melt(d3,id.vars=c('ID','chr','start','Subanalysis','Tissue','AvZ'))
d4$start <- d4$start/1000000
d4 %>% subset(chr=='chrZ') %>%
ggplot(aes(x=start,y=value))+
geom_point()+
facet_grid(Subanalysis~Tissue,scales='free')+
theme_minimal()

```

Bootstrapped F/M

```

library(dplyr)
library(tidyr)

### Begin with Chromosome 5mC data, calculate F/M first
#for F/M ratios
mfmeth <- read.table('Input.txt',header=TRUE)
mfmeth$mCG <- round(mfmeth$mCG,2)
head(mfmeth)

fmdat <- NULL
tissues <- c('Liver','Spleen')
for (organ in tissues) {
  cat('Working on tissue: ',organ,'\n')
  organ.df= subset(mfmeth,Tissue == organ)

  for (site in unique(organ.df$ID)) {
    cat('Working on region: ',site,'\n')

    fv=subset(organ.df, Sex == 'F' & ID == site)
    mv=subset(organ.df, Sex == 'M' & ID == site)

    vector.fm=c() # a vector per region

    for (r in 1:10000) {
      #sample, with replacement, the 5mC values from this region. Calculate the
      median within-sex
      fv2 = median(sample(fv$mCG,length(fv), replace=TRUE))
      mv2 = median(sample(mv$mCG,length(mv), replace=TRUE))
      #calculate F/M, but first change any zero values to 1%
      fv2[fv2==0] <- 0.01
      mv2[mv2==0] <- 0.01
      fmmed = fv2 / mv2
      vector.fm=append(vector.fm, fmmed)
    }
  }
}

```

```

}

### getting the CI
med.fm=median(vector.fm)
CI.fm=quantile(probs=c(0.025,0.975),x=vector.fm)
fm.dat=data.frame(med.fm,t(CI.fm))
fm.dat$Tissue <- organ; fm.dat$ID <- site
names(fm.dat) <- c('FMmedian','FMlowerCI','FMupperCI','Tissue','ID')
fmdat <- rbind(fmdat,fm.dat)
}
}

mfmeth2 <- merge(mfmeth,fmdat,by=c('Tissue','ID'))
write.table(mfmeth2,file='output.txt',quote=F,sep='\t',row.names=F)

```

And submit in parallel for expediency:

```

#!/bin/bash

#SBATCH --get-user-env
#SBATCH --mail-user=merondun@bio.lmu.de
#SBATCH --clusters=biohpc_gen
#SBATCH --partition=biohpc_gen_normal
#SBATCH --cpus-per-task=2
#SBATCH --mem-per-cpu=4763mb
#SBATCH --time=48:00:00

RUN=$1

mkdir Bootstrapped
mkdir Bootstrapped/${RUN}
mkdir bootstrapped_results

egrep -i "Subanalysis|${RUN}" mCG-10x_LongForm_ATAC-21Dec21.txt >
Bootstrapped/${RUN}/Input.txt
cp Bootstrap_FM.R Bootstrapped/${RUN}/Bootstrap_FM.R
cd Bootstrapped/${RUN}
Rscript Bootstrap_FM.R
cp Output.txt ../../bootstrapped_results/${RUN}.txt

```

Merge with the chromosome data:

```

library(tidyverse)
library(ggplot2)
library(viridis)

setwd('F:/Research/scratch/crow_atac/2022_05/bootstrapped_FM/')
d <- read.table('FM_Boot-2022-05-17.txt',header=T)
head(d)

d2 <- read.table('mCG-10x_LongForm_ATAC-21Dec21.txt',header=T)
d2 <- d2[,c('ID','length','AvZ','chr','Subanalysis','Tissue')]

```

```

#merge
d3 <- merge(d %>% select(-row),d2,by=c('ID','Tissue','Subanalysis')) %>% unique()

#add coordinates
d4 <- read.table('Coordinates.bed',header=F)
names(d4) <- c('chr','start','end','ID')

d5 <- merge(d3,d4,by=c('chr','ID'))
d5 <- d5 %>%
select(chr,start,end,ID,length,AvZ,Tissue,Subanalysis,median,lowerCI,upperCI)

#summary plots
d5 %>% subset(Subanalysis == 'gene') %>% ggplot(aes(x=chr,y=median,fill=AvZ))+
  geom_boxplot()+
  facet_grid(Tissue~.,scales='free')+
  theme_minimal()

write.table(d5,file='5mC_FM-Bootstrapped__2022-05-
17.txt',quote=F,sep='\t',row.names=F)

```

Identify CpG island compensation states, and create an overlapped master file:

```

cat *_Compensation.txt | bedtools sort -i - > Tissue_Compensation_Coordinates.bed
bedtools closest -a Tissue_Compensation_Coordinates.bed -b
Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.cgi.bed > Compensation_CGI_Overlapped.bed

```

And within R, overlap gene, CpG island, and methylation data:

```

setwd('/dss/dsslegfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-
0018/projects/2021__HybridZone_Epigenetics/ATACseq_Methylation_Analyses/2021_NOV/
Clip_9_Q20/2022_12_19')
.libPaths('~/.miniconda3/envs/r/lib/R/library')
library(dplyr)
library(tidyverse)
library(reshape2)
library(matrixStats)
library(viridis)
library(ggpubr)
library(rstatix)

mc = read.table('FM_Boot-2022-05-17.txt',header=TRUE)
mc = mc %>% dplyr::rename(mc = median,mc_lo = lowerCI,mc_hi = upperCI)
# d5 %>% filter(Subanalysis != 'chromosome') %>%
# mutate(chr = gsub('chr','',chr)) %>%
# ggplot(aes(x=chr,y=log2(median),fill=AvZ))+
# geom_boxplot()+ylab('Methylation (log2(f/m))')+
# facet_grid(Tissue~Subanalysis,scales='free')+
# theme_minimal()

cgi = read.table('Compensation_CGI_Overlapped.bed',header=FALSE)
cgi = cgi %>% dplyr::select(c(1,2,3,5,11,12,14,15,16,4))
names(cgi) =
c('chr','start','end','Tissue','state','gene','cgi_start','cgi_end','ID','rna_logf
m')
cgi$Subanalysis = 'cgi'

```

```

gene = read.table('Tissue_Compensation_Coordinates.bed')
gene = gene %>% dplyr::select(-c(v6,v7,v8,v9,v10))
names(gene) = c('chr', 'start', 'end', 'rna_logfm', 'Tissue', 'state', 'gene')
gene$Subanalysis = 'gene'
gene$cgi_start = NA
gene$cgi_end = NA
gene$ID = gene$gene
comp_dat = rbind(gene, cgi)
comp_dat = comp_dat %>% mutate(Tissue = gsub('spleen', 'Spleen', Tissue),
                               Tissue = gsub('liver', 'Liver', Tissue))

f = full_join(mc, comp_dat)
write.table(f, '5mC_CGI_Gene_2022-12-19.txt', quote=F, sep='\t', row.names=F)
f = read.table('5mC_CGI_Gene_2022-12-19.txt', header=TRUE)
fr = f %>% drop_na(rna_logfm) %>% drop_na(mc)

#calculate F/M
fm = fr %>% mutate(mclgfm = log2(mc))
fm = fm %>% mutate(state = gsub('partially_compensated', 'compensated', state))
fm = fm %>% mutate(state = gsub('compensated', 'DB', state),
                    state = gsub('not_compensated', 'Not_DB', state))
write.table(fm %>%
dplyr::select(!c(row, mc_lo, mc_hi)), file='Methylation_Over_Transcripts_CGI.txt', qu
ote=F, sep='\t', row.names=F)

#or start from here
fm = read.table('Methylation_Over_Transcripts_CGI.txt', header=T)
#rna and 5mc values are both log2 transformed already

#calculate rho between each 5mc and expression state (4 total comparisons)
fmrho = fm %>% group_by(chr, state, Tissue, Subanalysis) %>%
  summarize('log2(f/m) 5mC@log2(f/m) RNA' = cor(rna_logfm, mclgfm))

#make a label for plotting
rho_lab = fmrho %>% pivot_longer(!c(chr, state, Tissue, Subanalysis))
rho_lab = rho_lab %>% separate(name, into=c('methname', 'genename'), sep='@', remove =
T)

#plot correlations, here only for f-m for 5mC and log2(f/m) for RNA, change those
accordingly
fmp = fm %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=mclgfm, y=rna_logfm, col=state))+
  geom_point()+
  scale_color_manual(values=viridis(3))+
  geom_vline(xintercept=0, lty=2)+
  geom_hline(yintercept=0, lty=2)+
  xlab('Methylation (log2(f/m))')+ylab('Expression (log2(f/m))')+
  geom_text(data=rho_lab %>% filter(state == 'DB'), mapping =
(aes(x=Inf, y=Inf, label=paste0('p:
', signif(value, 2))))) , size=4, vjust=6, hjust=1.25)+
  geom_text(data=rho_lab %>% filter(state == 'not_DB'), mapping =
(aes(x=Inf, y=Inf, label=paste0('p:
', signif(value, 2))))) , size=4, vjust=7.5, hjust=1.25)+
  facet_grid(Tissue ~ Subanalysis, scales='free')+
  theme_classic()+
  theme(panel.border = element_rect(colour = "black", fill=NA, size=1))
fmp

```

```

pdf('Correlations_Expression_5mC.pdf',height=4,width=6,useDingbats = F)
fmp
dev.off()

#boxplots, here just show what the plot will look like, without significance test
fmd = fm %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=state,y=mclogfm,fill=state))+
  geom_boxplot(notch = TRUE)+ylab('Methylation (log2(f/m))')+
  facet_grid(Tissue ~ Subanalysis,scales='free')+
  geom_hline(yintercept=0,lty=2)+
  geom_vline(xintercept=0,lty=2)+
  scale_fill_manual(values=c('grey70','grey20'))+
  theme_classic()

pdf('Distributions_Expression_5mC.pdf',height=4,width=6)
fmd
dev.off()

#summarize
ft = fm %>% group_by(Subanalysis,Tissue,state) %>% summarize(median = median(mc),
                                                             mean = ci(mc)[1],
                                                             lo = ci(mc)[2],
                                                             hi=ci(mc)[3])
write.table(ft, file='FM_Summaries.txt',quote=F,sep='\t',row.names=F)

#test for significance with a t-test, implement a bonferonni correction based on
the tests done (by tissue, and by analysis reg v gene)
fmt = fm %>% select(ID,chr,state,Tissue,mclogfm,Subanalysis)
fmt$Tissue = factor(fmt$Tissue,levels=c('Liver','Spleen'))
stat.test <- fmt %>% ungroup %>%
  group_by(Tissue, Subanalysis) %>%
  t_test(data =.,mclogfm ~ state) %>%
  adjust_pvalue(method = "bonferroni") %>%
  add_significance('p.adj')
#t-test results
stat.test

# Tissue Subanalysis .y.      group1 group2    n1    n2 statistic    df    p
p.adj p.adj.signif
# * <fct> <chr>          <chr>  <chr>  <chr> <int> <int>    <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
<dbl> <chr>
# 1 Liver  cgi          mclogfm DB      not_DB  217  258    1.17  417. 0.243
0.972 ns
# 2 Liver  gene          mclogfm DB      not_DB  226  268   -1.61  492. 0.107
0.428 ns
# 3 Spleen cgi          mclogfm DB      not_DB  221  269   -1.34  482. 0.18
0.72  ns
# 4 Spleen gene          mclogfm DB      not_DB  237  299    0.289  534. 0.773 1
ns

#plot, should look the same as the above boxplot
ttp <- ggboxplot(
  fmt, x = "Tissue", y = "mclogfm",
  fill = "state",notch=TRUE,
  ggtheme = theme_pubr(border = TRUE)

```

```

) +
  scale_fill_manual(values=c('grey20','grey70'))+
  xlab('')+
  geom_hline(yintercept=0,lty=2)+
  facet_grid(.~Subanalysis)+
  ylab('Methylation (log2(f/m))')
ttp
# Add statistical test p-values to the plot
stat.test <- stat.test %>% add_xy_position(x = "Tissue",scales = 'free')
ttpa = ttp + stat_pvalue_manual(stat.test, label =
"p.adj.signif",bracket.nudge.y=0.2)
pdf('Distributions_States.pdf',height=6,width=7)
ttpa
dev.off()

```

DMPs: Gene-Based

```

#in bash
#awk '{OFS="\t"}{print $1, $8, $7, $9"_"$11"_"$10,$4, $5,$11}' mCG-
10x_LongForm_ATAC-21Dec21.txt | sed 's/SpLleen/M/g' | sed 's/Liver/L/g' | sed 'ld'
> DSS_Input.txt

#DSS: get DMRs
setwd('/dss/dss1egfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-
0018/projects/2021__HybridZone_Epigenetics/ATACseq_Methylation_Analyses/2021_NOV/
Clip_9_Q20')
.libPaths('~/.miniconda3/envs/methylation/lib/R/library')
library(DSS)
library(dplyr)
library(tidyr)
#library(maditr)
library(reshape2)
library(ggplot2)
library(forcats)

alldats <- read.table('mCG-10x_LongForm_ATAC-21Dec21.txt',header=TRUE)
chrdat = alldats %>% select(c(ID,length,AvZ,chr,Subanalysis))
alldats = alldats %>% dplyr::select(c(ID,cA,cM,Sample,chr,Subanalysis,Tissue))
names(alldats) <- c('loci','N','X','ID','chr','analysis','tissue')
#add a unique integer for each gene
andat <- NULL
for (sub in unique(alldats$analysis)) {
  cat('working on subanalysis: ',sub,'\n')
  sda <- subset(alldats,analysis==sub)

  #posm <- sda %>% select(loci,chr) %>% unique()
  #posm <- posm %>% group_by(chr) %>% mutate(pos = row_number())
  #sda <- merge(sda,posm,by=c('loci','chr'))
  sda$pos = 1

  tisdat <- NULL
  for (tis in unique(sda$tissue)) {
    cat('working on tissue: ',tis,'\n')
    td <- subset(sda,tissue==tis)

```

```

mdats <- td[,c('loci','pos','N','X','ID')]
mdats$pos <- as.integer(mdats$pos)
mdats = mdats %>% dplyr::rename(chr = loci)
mdats = mdats %>% arrange(chr,pos)
nrow(mdats)/4
allnames <- NULL

#loop through them..
for (samp in unique(mdats$ID)) {

  var <- mdats[grep1(samp,mdats$ID),][,1:4]

  cat('saved to variable: ',samp,'\n')
  #assign it to a new variable
  assign(paste0(samp),var)
  allnames <- unique(c(allnames,samp))

}

#get names
vars <- mget(allnames)

#create object
BSobj = makeBSseqData(vars,c(allnames))
BSobj

#import design
design <- read.table('WGBS_Metadat-DSS.txt',header=TRUE)
design = design %>% mutate(variable = gsub('_ADL','',design$variable),
                          Tissue = gsub('L$','Liver',Tissue),
                          Tissue = gsub('M$','Spleen',Tissue))
design <- subset(design,Tissue==tis)
X = model.matrix(~Sex, design)
X
DMLfit = DMLfit.multiFactor(BSobj, design=design, formula=~Sex)
vars <- colnames(DMLfit$X)[-1]
dmpdat <- NULL
for (vari in vars) {
  dats <- DMLtest.multiFactor(DMLfit,coef=vari)
  dats$var <- vari
  dmpdat <- rbind(dmpdat,dats)
}

#Reformat nicely
dmp <- dmpdat
dmp$var <- gsub('SexM','Sex',dmp$var)
dmp$tissue <- tis
dmp$Subanalysis = sub
tisdat <- rbind(tisdat,dmp)
}
andat <- rbind(andat,tisdat)
}
ddat <- andat
dd = data.frame(ID=ddat$chr,stat=ddat$stat,fdr=ddat$fdrs,Variable =
ddat$var,Tissue=ddat$tissue,Subanalysis = ddat$Subanalysis)
fd = left_join(dd,chrdat,by=c('ID','Subanalysis'))

```

```

fd = fd %>% mutate(signif = ifelse(fdr < 0.05, 'Significant', 'Non-Significant'))
fd = fd %>% unique
fdc = fd %>% group_by(chr, Tissue, AvZ, Subanalysis) %>% dplyr::count(signif)
fdp = fdc %>% mutate(chr = gsub('chr', '', chr)) %>%
  filter(Subanalysis != 'chromosome') %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=chr, fill=signif, y=n))+
  geom_bar(stat='identity')+
  facet_grid(Tissue~Subanalysis, scales='free')+
  scale_fill_manual(values=c('grey80', 'grey10'))+ylab('DMR Count')+
  theme_classic()
pdf('DmpCounts.pdf', height=6, width=10)
fdp
dev.off()

write.table(fd, 'WGBS-ATAC.DSS.FeatureBased-
10x.txt', quote=F, row.names=FALSE, sep='\t')
fd = read.table('WGBS-ATAC.DSS.FeatureBased-10x.txt', header=TRUE)

```

Manhattan

Plot those results:

```

setwd('/dss/dss1egfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-
0018/projects/2021__HybridZone_Epigenetics/ATACseq_Methylation_Analyses/2021_NOV/
Clip_9_Q20')
.libPaths('~/.miniconda3/envs/r/lib/R/library')
#Plot Genome-wide Estimates and DMPs
library(DSS)
library(dplyr)
library(tidyr)
library(maditr)
library(reshape2)
library(karyoploteR)
library(viridis)
library(ggplot2)
library(LICORS)
library(forcats)

#init legwork
class <- read.table('WGBS-ATAC.DSS.FeatureBased-10x.txt', header=TRUE)
#add field whether or not its significant
class$chr <- gsub('chr', '', class$chr)

#also add bootstrapped F/M values, log transform them
fm = read.table('2022_12_19/5mC_FM-Bootstrapped__2022-05-17.txt', header=TRUE)
fm = fm %>% select(-c(chr,))
fd = full_join(fm %>% select(-c(AvZ, length)), class)
#add shapes and colors for subanalysis
fd = fd %>% mutate(Color = ifelse(Subanalysis == 'cgi', 'purple', 'gold'),
  shape = ifelse(Subanalysis == 'cgi', 8, 16))

#add lengths
len <- read.table('genome5.6.bed', header=FALSE)
names(len) <- c('chr', 'start', 'length')

```

```

len$chr <- gsub('chr','',len$chr)
len <- subset(len,chr!='23')
chrLen <- len %>% select(-start)
cols = viridis(3,option='mako')

#Set up genome, and chr Z genome
crowG = makeGRangesFromDataFrame(len,seqnames.field = 'chr',start.field =
'start',end.field = 'length')
crowZ = makeGRangesFromDataFrame(subset(len,chr=='Z'),seqnames.field =
'chr',start.field = 'start',end.field = 'length')

##### PLOT: Manhattan #####
view <- 'chrZ'
view <- 'WG'
png('Whole-Genome.Manhattan-ATAC.png',height=6,width=10,units='in',res=600,bg =
"white")
png('ChrZ.Manhattan-ATAC.png',height=6,width=10,units='in',res=600,bg = "white")
#Plot Base
pp <- getDefaultPlotParams(plot.type=4)
pp$leftmargin <- 0.08

if(view=='chrZ'){
  #if chrZ, plot this
  kp <- plotKaryotype(plot.type=4, genome = crowZ,plot.params = pp)
  kpAddBaseNumbers(kp,tick.dist = 25000000,cex=0.7)
} else {
  kp <- plotKaryotype(plot.type=4, genome = crowG,plot.params =
pp,labels.plotter=NULL)
  #for staggered chr names
  evens <- ((1:length(len$chr))%2)==0
  chr.names <- kp$chromosomes
  even.names <- chr.names
  even.names[!evens] <- ""
  odd.names <- chr.names
  odd.names[evens] <- ""

  kpAddChromosomeNames(kp, chr.names = odd.names,cex=0.7)
  kpAddChromosomeNames(kp, chr.names = even.names, yoffset = -7,cex=0.7)
}

run <- 'fd'
vars <- c('Liver','Spleen')
tracks <- length(vars)*2

counter <- 0
for (varz in vars) {
  counter <- counter+1
  cat('Current Autotrack: ',counter,' for FDR ',varz,'\n')
  at <- autotrack(current.track = counter, total.tracks = tracks);
  at$r1 <- at$r1-0.05
  data <- get(run)
  dat <- data %>% filter(Tissue == varz)

  #add pvalues

```

```

kpPoints(kp, chr = dat$chr, x=dat$start, y=-log10(dat$fdr),
        col=dat$Color,pch=dat$Shape,cex=0.75,
        ymin=-log10(1),ymax=max(-log10(dat$fdr)),r0=at$r0, r1=at$r1);
kpAxis(kp, ymin =-log10(1), ymax=max(-log10(dat$fdr)),cex=0.8,r0=at$r0,
r1=at$r1,col="black");
kpAddLabels(kp,cex=0.7,labels = paste0('-log10(p) ',varz),r0=at$r0+.23,
r1=at$r1,col="black",srt=90,label.margin = 0.07)
kpAbline(kp, h=-log10(0.05),ymin=-log10(1),ymax=max(-log10(dat$fdr)),r0=at$r0,
r1=at$r1, col="black", lwd=1,lty=2)
kpAbline(kp, h=0, r0=at$r0, r1=at$r1, col="black", lwd=1,lty=1)

#and plot log2(F/M)
counter <- counter+1
cat('Current Autotrack: ',counter,' for F/M ',varz,'\n')
at <- autotrack(current.track = counter, total.tracks = tracks);
at$r1 <- at$r1-0.05
kpPoints(kp, chr = dat$chr, x=dat$start, y=log2(dat$median),
        col=dat$Color,pch=dat$Shape,cex=0.75,
        ymin=min(log2(dat$median)),ymax=max(log2(dat$median)),r0=at$r0,
r1=at$r1);
kpAxis(kp, ymin =min(log2(dat$median)),
ymax=max(log2(dat$median)),cex=0.8,r0=at$r0, r1=at$r1,col="black");
kpAddLabels(kp,cex=0.7,labels = paste0('log2(F/M) ',varz),r0=at$r0+.23,
r1=at$r1,col="black",srt=90,label.margin = 0.07)
#kpAbline(kp, h=0,r0=at$r0, r1=at$r1, col="black", lwd=1,lty=2)

}

dev.off()

```

Base-Pair Resolution, DMP Detection

All Together, overlap 5mC data:

```

library(dplyr)
library(tidyr)
library(reshape2)
library(matrixStats)

#grab all files
files <- list.files(path=".", pattern="*.cov.gz", full.names=TRUE,
recursive=FALSE)
allnames <- NULL

#loop through them..
for (samp in files) {

  cat('Reading in file: ',samp,'\n')
  #read data
  ztab <- gzfile(samp,'rt');

```

```

tab <- read.table(ztab,header=F);

#extract name which will be our new variable
name <- gsub('./',' ',samp)
name <- gsub('.CpG_5mC.cov.gz',' ',name)

#only keep positions with >9x (autosomes, Z on male), or >4x (Z on female)
rm(covZ)
cov <- 9
if(grep('_F$',name)=='TRUE'){
  print('FEMALE, setting coverage to 4x on Z')
  covZ <- 4
} else {
  print('MALE, setting coverage to 9x on Z')
  covZ <- 9
}

tab <- subset(tab,(V1 == 'chrZ' & (V5 + V6) > covZ) | (V1 != 'chrZ' & (V5 + V6)
> cov))
tab$site <- paste0(tab$V1,'_',tab$V2)
tab$V4 <- tab$V4/100

#grab only site / countM / countU / %5mC
tab2 <- tab[,c(7,5,6,4)]
names(tab2) <- c('site',paste0('Cs_',name),paste0('Ts_',name),name);

cat('Saved to variable: ',name,'\n')
#assign it to a new variable
assign(paste0(name),tab2)

#add this sample to our total list
allnames <- unique(c(allnames,name))
}

#get names
vars <- mget(allnames)
# merge the points, keeping all
masterWGBS <- Reduce(function(x,y) merge(x = x, y = y,
by=c('site'),all=TRUE),vars)

write.table(masterWGBS,file='Step1.txt',quote=F,row.names=FALSE,sep='\t')

#filter according to missingness, if there's any missing individuals, drop
the site
covdat <- masterWGBS[rowSums(is.na(masterWGBS[grep('^Cs_', names(masterWGBS))]))
== 0, ]

#and filter for maximum coverage:
covs <- covdat[grep('^site|^Cs_|^Ts_',names(covdat))]
covs$total <- rowSums(covs[grep('^Ts_|Cs_',names(covs))],na.rm=TRUE)
thresh <- quantile(covs$total,0.999)
keep <- subset(covs,total < thresh)
keep <- keep[grep('^site$',names(keep))]

#calculate variable divergence
p5mC <- masterWGBS[grep('^AD_|^H_|^S_',names(masterWGBS))]

```

```

masterWGBS$Species <- (rowMeans(p5mC[grep1('^D_', names(p5mC))], na.rm=TRUE) -
rowMeans(p5mC[grep1('^S_', names(p5mC))], na.rm=TRUE))
masterWGBS$Tissue <- (rowMeans(p5mC[grep1('^M_', names(p5mC))], na.rm=TRUE) -
rowMeans(p5mC[grep1('^L_', names(p5mC))], na.rm=TRUE))
masterWGBS$Sex <- (rowMeans(p5mC[grep1('^F$', names(p5mC))], na.rm=TRUE) -
rowMeans(p5mC[grep1('^M$', names(p5mC))], na.rm=TRUE))

divdats <- masterWGBS[grep1('^site$|Species$|Tissue$|Sex$', names(masterWGBS))]

#filter those
maxcov <- merge(keep, divdats, by='site')
maxcov2 <- merge(maxcov, covdat, by='site')
masterWGBSf <- maxcov2

#remove sites with low variance, and sites undiverged
#calculate site-level range of 5mC values, and site-level variance
masterWGBSf$Divergence <-
rowMaxs(as.matrix(masterWGBSf[grep1('^S_|^D_|^H_', names(masterWGBSf))]), na.rm=TRUE) -
rowMins(as.matrix(masterWGBSf[grep1('^S_|^D_|^H_', names(masterWGBSf))]), na.rm=TRUE)
masterWGBSf$Variance <-
apply(masterWGBSf[grep1('^S_|^D_|^H_', names(masterWGBSf))], 1, var, na.rm=TRUE)

#assess all the filters
# merged / individual missing data / CpG number filter / maximum coverage
nrow(masterWGBS)
nrow(covdat)
nrow(maxcov2)

masterWGBS <- masterWGBSf[!grep1('^aminsite|^sites_', names(masterWGBSf))]

#Our data is in a poor format for looping. To fix this we can transform it long-
form
Cs <- masterWGBS[grep1('^site|^Cs_', names(masterWGBS))]
Csm <- melt(Cs, id.vars=c('site'))
Csm$variable <- gsub('Cs_', '', Csm$variable)
names(Csm)[names(Csm) == 'value'] <- 'Cs'

#and thymines
Ts <- masterWGBS[grep1('^site|^Ts_', names(masterWGBS))]
Tsm <- melt(Ts, id.vars=c('site'))
Tsm$variable <- gsub('Ts_', '', Tsm$variable)
names(Tsm)[names(Tsm) == 'value'] <- 'Ts'

#merge
CT <- merge(Csm, Tsm, by=c('site', 'variable'))

#short-form for PCAs, etc, still has the divergence data
write.table(masterWGBS, 'WGBS_PCA_Input-10x.txt', quote=F, row.names=FALSE)

#now ready for model
write.table(CT, file="WGBS_GLMM-10x.txt", row.names=FALSE, quote=F, col.names=TRUE)

#also save long form
library(tidyverse)

```

```

d <- CT
names(d) <- c('ID', 'Sample', 'mC', 'mT')
d$mCA <- d$mC+d$mT
d$mCG <- d$mC/d$mCA
d <- d %>% select(-mT)
d$BAK <- d$Sample
d <- d %>% separate(BAK,into=c('Species', 'Locality', 'Num', 'Tissue', 'Age', 'Sex'))
d <- d %>% select(-c(Species,Locality,Num,Age))
d$Tissue <- gsub('L', 'Liver', d$Tissue)
d$Tissue <- gsub('M', 'Spleen', d$Tissue)
d$Subanalysis <- 'BasePair'
write.table(d, file='mCG-10x_LongForm_BasePair-2022-05-18.txt', quote=F, sep='\t', row.names=F)

```

DSS: DMP Detection

```

#DSS: get DMRs
source('~/modules/R_Functions.R')
library(DSS)
library(dplyr)
library(tidyr)
library(maditr)
library(reshape2)

alldats <- read.table('WGBS_GLMM-10x.txt', header=TRUE)
alldats$TC <- alldats$Cs+alldats$Ts
mdats <- alldats[,c('site', 'TC', 'Cs', 'variable')]
mdats <- mdats %>% separate(site, c('chr', 'pos'))
mdats <- mdats[!grepl('garbage', names(mdats))]
names(mdats) <- c('chr', 'pos', 'N', 'X', 'ID')
mdats$pos <- as.integer(mdats$pos)
mdats <- mdats %>% arrange(chr, pos)
nrow(mdats)/8
rm(alldats)

allnames <- NULL
#loop through them..
for (samp in unique(mdats$ID)) {

  var <- mdats[grepl(samp, mdats$ID), ][, 1:4]

  cat('saved to variable: ', samp, '\n')
  #assign it to a new variable
  assign(paste0(samp), var)
  allnames <- unique(c(allnames, samp))

}

#get names
vars <- mget(allnames)

#create object
BSobj = makeBSseqData(vars, c(allnames))
BSobj

```

```

#import design
design <- read.table('WGBS_Metadat-DSS.txt',header=TRUE)
X = model.matrix(~Tissue+Sex, design)
X
DMLfit = DMLfit.multiFactor(BSobj, design=design, formula=~Tissue+Sex)
vars <- colnames(DMLfit$X)[-1]
dmpdat <- NULL
dmrdat <- NULL
for (vari in vars) {
  dats <- DMLtest.multiFactor(DMLfit,coef=vari)
  dats$var <- vari
  dmpdat <- rbind(dmpdat,dats)
  dmr <- callDMR(dats,minCG=4,p.threshold=0.05)
  dmr$var <- vari
  dmrdat <- rbind(dmrdat,dmr)
}

#Save DMR
write.table(dmrdat,file='WGBS_DMRs-10x.txt',quote=F,sep='\t',row.names=F)
#Reformat nicely
dmp <- dmpdat
dmp <- rename.col(dmp,'pos','start')
write.table(dmp,file='Step2.txt',quote=F,sep='\t',row.names=FALSE)
dmp <- read.table('Step2.txt',header=T)
dmp$var <- gsub('SexM','Sex',dmp$var);dmp$var <- gsub('TissueM','Tissue',dmp$var)
dmp$site <- paste0(dmp$chr,'_',dmp$start)
pca <- read.table('WGBS_PCA_Input-10x.txt',header=TRUE)
pca$Tissue <- (rowMeans(pca[grep1('_M_ADL', names(pca))],na.rm=TRUE) -
rowMeans(pca[grep1('_L_ADL', names(pca))],na.rm=TRUE))
pca1 <- pca[grep1('^site|Sex|Tissue$',names(pca))]
pca2 <- melt(pca1,id.vars=c('site'),variable.name = 'var',value.name =
'divergence')
wgbss <- merge(pca2,dmp,by=c('site','var'))
wgbss <- wgbss %>% mutate(Signif = ifelse(fdrs < 0.05,'Significant','Non-
Significant'))
write.table(wgbss,'WGBS-ATAC.DSS.BP-10x.txt',quote=F,row.names=FALSE,sep='\t')

```

Plot: Manhattan

```

setwd('F:/Research/scratch/crow_atac/2022_05/manhattan/')

#Plot Genome-wide Estimates and DMPs
library(DSS)
library(dplyr)
library(tidyr)
library(maditr)
library(reshape2)
library(karyoploteR)
library(viridis)
library(ggplot2)
library(LICORS)
library(forcats)

cols <- viridis(4)
#init legwork

```

```

class <- read.table('WGBS-ATAC.DSS.BP-10x.txt',header=TRUE)
class <- class %>% mutate(Color1=ifelse(var=='Sex',cols[2],cols[1]))
#add field whether or not its significant
dats1 <- class %>% mutate(Color = ifelse(fdrs < 0.05 ,Color1,'black')) %>%
select(-Color1)
dats1$chr <- gsub('chr','',dats1$chr)

#add lengths
len <- read.table('genome5.6.bed',header=FALSE)
names(len) <- c('chr','start','length')
len$chr <- gsub('chr','',len$chr)
len <- subset(len,chr!='23')
chr1en <- len %>% select(-start)

#count DMPs
dats1 <- merge(dats1,chr1en,by='chr')
dmps <- dats1 %>% group_by(chr,length,signif,var) %>% count()
dmps$chr <- factor(dmps$chr,levels=chr1en$chr)

dmp1ot <- dmps %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=chr,y=n,fill=signif))+
  facet_grid(var~.,scales='free')+
  scale_fill_manual(values=c('black','goldenrod1'))+
  theme_classic()+
  geom_bar(stat='identity')

pdf('DMPs_By_Variable.pdf',height=6,width=9)
dmp1ot
dev.off()

#Set up genome, only chr Z
genome <- read.table('genome5.6.bed',header=FALSE)
genome <- genome[!grep('chr23',genome$V1),]
genome$V1 <- gsub('chr','',genome$V1)
crowG <- makeGRangesFromDataFrame(genome,seqnames.field = 'V1',start.field =
'V2',end.field = 'V3')

##### PLOT: Manhattan #####
view <- 'chrZ'
view <- 'WG'
png('Whole-Genome.Manhattan-ATAC-Sex.png',height=6,width=10,units='in',res=600,bg
= "transparent")
png('ChrZ.Manhattan-ATAC.png',height=6,width=10,units='in',res=600,bg =
"transparent")
#pdf('Whole-Genome.Manhattan-ATAC-Sex.pdf',height=6,width=10)
#Plot Base
pp <- getDefaultPlotParams(plot.type=4)
pp$leftmargin <- 0.08

if(view=='chrZ'){
  #if chrZ, plot this
  kp <- plotKaryotype(plot.type=4, genome =
subset(crowG,seqnames=='Z'),plot.params = pp)
  kpAddBaseNumbers(kp,tick.dist = 25000000,cex=0.7)
} else {

```

```

kp <- plotKaryotype(plot.type=4, genome = crowd,plot.params =
pp,labels.plotter=NULL)
#for staggered chr names
evens <- ((1:length(genome$chr))%2)==0
chr.names <- kp$chromosomes
even.names <- chr.names
even.names[!evens] <- ""
odd.names <- chr.names
odd.names[evens] <- ""

kpAddChromosomeNames(kp, chr.names = odd.names,cex=0.7)
kpAddChromosomeNames(kp, chr.names = even.names, yoffset = -7,cex=0.7)

}

run <- 'dats1'
vars <- c('Sex','Tissue')
tracks <- length(vars)+2

counter <- 0
for (varz in vars) {
  counter <- counter+1
  cat('Current Autotrack: ',counter,' for ',varz,'\n')
  at <- autotrack(current.track = counter, total.tracks = tracks);
  at$r1 <- at$r1-0.05
  data <- get(run)
  dat <- data[grep1(varz,data$var),];
  palette(c('black',cols[[counter]]));

  #add pvalues
  kpPoints(kp, chr = dat$chr, x=dat$start, y=-log10(dat$fdrs),
           col=as.character(dat$color),pch=16,cex=0.75,
           ymin=-log10(1),ymax=max(-log10(dat$fdr)),r0=at$r0, r1=at$r1);
  kpAxis(kp, ymin =-log10(1), ymax=max(-log10(dat$fdr)),cex=0.8,r0=at$r0,
r1=at$r1,col="black");
  kpAddLabels(kp,cex=0.8,labels = paste0('-log10(p) ',varz),r0=at$r0+.18,
r1=at$r1,col="black",srt=90,label.margin = 0.07)
  kpAbline(kp, h=-log10(0.05),ymin=-log10(1),ymax=max(-log10(dat$fdr)),r0=at$r0,
r1=at$r1, col="black", lwd=1,lty=2)
  kpAbline(kp, h=0, r0=at$r0, r1=at$r1, col="black", lwd=1,lty=1)

}

#now add log2(F/M) values for the two tissues, from bootstrap data
run2 <- 'fmdat'
vari <- c('Liver','Spleen')

for (va in vari) {
  counter <- counter+1
  cat('Current Autotrack: ',counter,' for ',va,'\n')
  at <- autotrack(current.track = counter, total.tracks = tracks);
  at$r1 <- at$r1-0.05
  data <- get(run2)
  dat <- data[grep1(va,data$Tissue),];
  palette(c('black',cols[[counter]]));

```

```

#add pvalues
kpPoints(kp, chr = dat$chr, x=dat$start, y=log2(dat$FM),
         col=as.character(dat$Color),pch=16,cex=0.75,
         ymin=-log10(1),ymax=max(-log10(dat$fdr)),r0=at$r0, r1=at$r1);
kpAxis(kp, ymin =-log10(1), ymax=max(-log10(dat$fdr)),cex=0.8,r0=at$r0,
r1=at$r1,col="black");
kpAddLabels(kp,cex=0.8,labels = paste0('-log10(p) ',varz),r0=at$r0+.18,
r1=at$r1,col="black",srt=90,label.margin = 0.07)
kpAbline(kp, h=-log10(0.05),ymin=-log10(1),ymax=max(-log10(dat$fdr)),r0=at$r0,
r1=at$r1, col="black", lwd=1,lty=2)
kpAbline(kp, h=0, r0=at$r0, r1=at$r1, col="black", lwd=1,lty=1)

}

dev.off()

```

Bootstrapped Ratios

```

setwd('F:/Research/scratch/crow_atac/2022_05/bootstrapped_FM/')
library(dplyr)
library(tidyr)
library(ggplot2)
library(data.table)

### Begin with 5mC data
mfmeth <- fread('mCG-10x_LongForm_ATAC-21Dec21-Coordinates.txt.gz',header=T) %>%
as.data.frame
mfmeth <- mfmeth %>% subset(Subanalysis != 'chromosome')

#round to 2 digits
mfmeth$mCG <- round(mfmeth$mCG,2)
head(mfmeth)
mfmeth %>% mutate(chr=gsub('chr',' ',chr)) %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=chr,y=mCG,fill=Sex))+geom_boxplot()+
  facet_grid(Subanalysis~Tissue)+ylim(c(0,1))+theme_classic()+
  scale_fill_manual(values=c('cadetblue2','cadetblue'))+
  ylab('% 5mC')

#Ana's Bootstrapping for Z:A Ratio
sub1 <- NULL
for (sub in unique(mfmeth$Subanalysis)) {
  #First, grab only 1 subanalysis at a time: chromosome / gene / CpG island
  cat('working on subanalysis: ', sub,'\n')
  sda <- subset(mfmeth,Subanalysis == sub)
  zdat <- NULL
  tissues <- c('Liver','Spleen')
  for (organ in tissues) {
    #Then, grab only tissue data. Then, grab the Z data directly
    cat('working on tissue: ', organ,'\n')
    organ.df=subset(sda,Tissue==organ)
    Zf=subset(organ.df, Sex == 'F' & AvZ == 'chrZ' & start >= 688000)$mCG
    Pf=subset(organ.df, Sex == 'F' & AvZ == 'chrZ' & start < 688000)$mCG
    Af=subset(organ.df, Sex == 'F' & AvZ != 'chrZ')
    Zm=subset(organ.df, Sex == 'M' & AvZ == 'chrZ' & start >= 688000)$mCG
  }
}

```

```

Pm=subset(organ.df, Sex == 'M' & AvZ == 'chrZ' & start < 688000)$mCG
Am=subset(organ.df, Sex == 'M' & AvZ != 'chrZ')
sexdat <- NULL
#chrdat <- NULL

#for (chrs in unique(Am$chr)) {
  #now loop through each chromosome for Sex
  #cat('working on chromosome: ', chrs,'\n')
  Cf <- subset(Af, chr != 'chr_Z')$mCG
  Cm <- subset(Am, chr != 'chr_Z')$mCG
  vector.fZA=c() # a vector per chromosome
  vector.mZA=c()
  vector.fZP=c()
  vector.mZP=c()
  vector.A.fm=c()
  vector.Z.fm=c()
  vector.P.fm=c()

  for (r in 1:10000) {
    Z.boot.f = sample(Zf,length(Zf), replace=TRUE)
    P.boot.f = sample(Pf,length(Pf), replace=TRUE)
    C.boot.f = sample(Cf,length(Cf), replace=TRUE)
    Z.boot.m = sample(Zm, length(Zm), replace=TRUE)
    P.boot.m = sample(Pm, length(Pm), replace=TRUE)
    C.boot.m = sample(Cm, length(Cm), replace=TRUE)
    ### calculating the median
    median.Zf.boot=median(Z.boot.f)
    median.Pf.boot=median(P.boot.f)
    median.Cf.boot=median(C.boot.f)
    median.Zm.boot=median(Z.boot.m)
    median.Pm.boot=median(P.boot.m)
    median.Cm.boot=median(C.boot.m)

    ### getting the ratios: Z:A first
    ZA.f= median.Zf.boot / median.Cf.boot
    ZA.m= median.Zm.boot / median.Cm.boot
    vector.fZA=append(vector.fZA, ZA.f)
    vector.mZA=append(vector.mZA, ZA.m)

    ### getting the ratios: Z:PAR
    ZP.f= median.Zf.boot / median.Pf.boot
    ZP.m= median.Zm.boot / median.Pm.boot
    vector.fZP=append(vector.fZP, ZP.f)
    vector.mZP=append(vector.mZP, ZP.m)

    ### getting the ratios: now FM
    #FM autosomes
    A.fm = median.Cf.boot / median.Cm.boot
    vector.A.fm=append(vector.A.fm,A.fm)
    #FM chr Z
    Z.fm = median.Zf.boot / median.Zm.boot
    vector.Z.fm=append(vector.Z.fm,Z.fm)
    #FM PAR
    P.fm = median.Pf.boot / median.Pm.boot
    vector.P.fm=append(vector.P.fm,P.fm)
  }
}

```

```

}

### getting the CI
med.fZA=median(vector.fZA)
med.mZA=median(vector.mZA)
med.fZP=median(vector.fZP)
med.mZP=median(vector.mZP)
med.A.fm=median(vector.A.fm)
med.Z.fm=median(vector.Z.fm)
med.P.fm=median(vector.P.fm)

CI.fZA=quantile(probs=c(0.025,0.975),x=vector.fZA)
CI.mZA=quantile(probs=c(0.025,0.975),x=vector.mZA)
CI.fZP=quantile(probs=c(0.025,0.975),x=vector.fZP)
CI.mZP=quantile(probs=c(0.025,0.975),x=vector.mZP)
CI.A.fm=quantile(probs=c(0.025,0.975),x=vector.A.fm)
CI.Z.fm=quantile(probs=c(0.025,0.975),x=vector.Z.fm)
CI.P.fm=quantile(probs=c(0.025,0.975),x=vector.P.fm)

#bind them into an intelligible frame
#F:ZA
f.datZA=data.frame(med.fZA,t(CI.fZA))
f.datZA$Tissue <- organ; f.datZA$Subanalysis <- sub; f.datZA$Parameter <-
'zf:AAf'
names(f.datZA) <-
c('median','lowerCI','upperCI','Tissue','Subanalysis','Parameter')
#M:ZA
m.datZA=data.frame(med.mZA,t(CI.mZA))
m.datZA$Tissue <- organ; m.datZA$Subanalysis <- sub; m.datZA$Parameter <-
'Zzm:AAm'
names(m.datZA) <-
c('median','lowerCI','upperCI','Tissue','Subanalysis','Parameter')
#F:ZP
f.datZP=data.frame(med.fZP,t(CI.fZP))
f.datZP$Tissue <- organ; f.datZP$Subanalysis <- sub; f.datZP$Parameter <-
'zf:PARzf'
names(f.datZP) <-
c('median','lowerCI','upperCI','Tissue','Subanalysis','Parameter')
#M:ZP
m.datZP=data.frame(med.mZP,t(CI.mZP))
m.datZP$Tissue <- organ; m.datZP$Subanalysis <- sub; m.datZP$Parameter <-
'Zzm:PARZzm'
names(m.datZP) <-
c('median','lowerCI','upperCI','Tissue','Subanalysis','Parameter')
#A: F/M
fm.datA=data.frame(med.A.fm,t(CI.A.fm))
fm.datA$Tissue <- organ; fm.datA$Subanalysis <- sub; fm.datA$Parameter <-
'AAf:AAm'
names(fm.datA) <-
c('median','lowerCI','upperCI','Tissue','Subanalysis','Parameter')
#Z: F/M
fm.datZ=data.frame(med.Z.fm,t(CI.Z.fm))
fm.datZ$Tissue <- organ; fm.datZ$Subanalysis <- sub; fm.datZ$Parameter <-
'zf:ZZm'
names(fm.datZ) <-
c('median','lowerCI','upperCI','Tissue','Subanalysis','Parameter')

```

```

#P: F/M
fm.datP=data.frame(med.P.fm,t(CI.P.fm))
fm.datP$Tissue <- organ; fm.datP$Subanalysis <- sub; fm.datP$Parameter <-
'PARZf:PARZZm'
names(fm.datP) <-
c('median','lowerCI','upperCI','Tissue','Subanalysis','Parameter')

all <- rbind(f.datZA,m.datZA,f.datZP,m.datZP,fm.datA,fm.datZ,fm.datP)

#}
zadat <- rbind(zadat,all)
}
subl <- rbind(subl,zadat)
}

write.table(subl,'Bootstrap_Ratios.txt',quote=F,sep='\t',row.names=F)

```

5mC - ATACseq Peaks

We will investigate methylation patterns +/- 2KB from each ATACseq peak. To do this, We will:

- extract each sample from the ATACseq and RNAseq file, as this analysis is sample-specific
- extract each peak coordinates from the ATACseq file
- extend each peak by 2KB in either direction
- perform a left outer join on the 5mC data and RNAseq data (5mC positions can contribute to multiple peaks)

```

#!/bin/bash

#SBATCH --get-user-env
#SBATCH --mail-user=merondun@bio.lmu.de
#SBATCH --clusters=biohpc_gen
#SBATCH --partition=biohpc_gen_normal
#SBATCH --cpus-per-task=5
#SBATCH --time=24:00:00

samp=$1

mkdir tmp
mkdir tmp/$samp

#subset sample's peaks
grep $samp ATAC_Reduced.bed | awk '{print $4}' | sed '1d' | sort | uniq >
tmp/$samp/ATAC-IDs.list
grep $samp ATAC_Reduced.bed > tmp/$samp/ATAC-Samp.txt
#clear up previous runs
rm tmp/$samp/*.bed

#for each sample and for each peak, create a bed file which includes +/- 2 KB
from the peak's start and end coordinates
for peak in $(cat tmp/$samp/ATAC-IDs.list); do

```

```

echo "Extracting peak ${peak}"
#grab pvalue, summit, and fpkm
grep -w $peak tmp/$samp/ATAC-Samp.txt > tmp/$samp/ATAC-Peak.txt
bedtools slop -i tmp/$samp/ATAC-Peak.txt -g crow_5.6.genome -b 2000 >>
tmp/$samp/Master.bed

done
#subset sample's peaks
bedtools intersect -wo -a $samp*.CpG_5mC.cov -b tmp/$samp/Master.bed | cut -f7 --
complement | sort | uniq | bgzip -c > $samp.5mC_Peaks.bed.gz

```

2KB Peaks

Within R:

```

#Plot Median 5mC Values around ATAC-seq Peaks
setwd('~/.files/atacseq')
source('~/.R_Functions-RF.R')
library(tidyverse)
library(dplyr)
library(gmodels)
library(reshape2)
library(ggplot2)
library(viridis)

#grab all files
d <- read.table('Master-ExactOverlap.bed',header=T)
names(d) <-
c('chr', 'start', 'end', 'methp', 'cc', 'cu', 'peak_start', 'peak_end', 'peakID', 'tissue',
'fold_change', 'gene_fpkm', 'zfpm', 'sample', 'overlap')
d <- d %>% mutate(AvZ = ifelse(chr=='chrZ', 'Z', 'Autosome'))
#plot levels around peaks
d1 <- d
#first find peak midpoints
d1$flank_start <- d1$peak_start + 2000
d1$flank_end <- d1$peak_end - 2000
d1$peak_size <- abs(d1$flank_end - d1$flank_start)
d1$midpoint <- ((d1$peak_end - d1$peak_start)/2) + d1$peak_start
d1$distance <- d1$start - d1$midpoint
#remove any 5mC positions which are further than 2KB from the centroid
d2 <- subset(d1, abs(distance) < 2000)
d4 <- d2
d4$distance <- round(d4$distance,0)
#divide the 4KB total region into 40BP windows (n=100)
cuts <- seq(-2000,2000,40)
ints <- seq(1,100,1)
labs <- seq(-2000,1960,40)
#Assign them an interval label
d4 <- d4 %>% mutate(Interval=cut(distance,breaks=cuts,labels=labs,right=FALSE))
d5 <- subset(d4,sample != '.')

#find IQR outliers for gene_fpkm intra-individually/tissue
tis <- read.table('ATAC_Reduced.bed',header=T)
tis <- tis %>% mutate(AvZ = ifelse(chr=='chrZ', 'Z', 'Autosome'))

```

```

fpkmthresh <- tis %>% group_by(sampID,AvZ) %>%
summarize(Threshold=quantile(log10(gene_fpkm),0.9))
fpkmthresh <- fpkmthresh %>% rename(sample=sampID)
d6 <- merge(d5,fpkmthresh,by=c('AvZ','sample'))
d6 <- d6 %>% mutate(Expressed = ifelse(log10(gene_fpkm) >
Threshold,'Expressed','Unexpressed'))
d6 %>% group_by(sample) %>% count(Expressed)
d7 <- d6 %>% drop_na(Interval)

#calculate the median 95% CIs
stats <- d7 %>% group_by(sample,Interval,AvZ,Expressed) %>%
  summarize(DOliveCIproc(methp,alpha=0.05))
#save the results
write.table(stats,file='Distance_2KB_IQR_Results-N40-Expressed-AvZ-
90IQR.txt',quote=F,sep='\t',row.names=F)
stats <- read.table('Distance_2KB_IQR_Results-N40-Expressed-AvZ-
90IQR.txt',header=T)
stats$BAK <- stats$sample
stats <- stats %>% separate(BAK, into=c('Taxon','Locality','Num','Tissue')) %>%
na.omit()
stats <- stats %>% mutate(Sex = ifelse(grepl('D_Ko_C31',sample)==TRUE,'Male',
ifelse(grepl('D_Ko_C45',sample)==TRUE,'Female',
ifelse(grepl('S_Up_H59',sample)==TRUE,'Male',
ifelse(grepl('S_Up_H60',sample)==TRUE,'Female','wrong')))))

cols <- viridis(5)
stats$Interval <- gsub(1960,2000,stats$Interval)
stats$Interval <- as.numeric(stats$Interval)
peaks <- ggplot(stats,aes(x=Interval))+
  geom_line(aes(y=Median,col=Sex))+
  #geom_point(aes(y=Median,col=Sex),pch=16,size=1.5)+
  #geom_errorbar(aes(ymin=LCI,ymax=UCI,col=Sex))+
  theme_minimal(base_size=14)+
  ylab('% 5mC CpG Methylation')+xlab('Distance from ATAC Peak Centroid (BP)')+
  scale_color_manual(values=c('cadetblue2','cadetblue'))+
  scale_fill_manual(values=c('cadetblue2','cadetblue'))+
  facet_grid(Tissue+Taxon~AvZ+Expressed)+
  ylim(c(0,100))+
  scale_x_continuous(labels = c('-2000','0','2000'), breaks = c(-2000,0,2000))+
  theme(panel.spacing.x = unit(8, "mm"))
peaks

pdf('5mC_ATAC_PeakActivity-2KB-90IQR.pdf',height=6,width=9)
peaks
dev.off()

```

10KB Peaks

```
#Plot Median 5mC values around ATAC-seq Peaks
setwd('~/.files/atacseq')
source('~/.R_Functions-RF.R')
library(tidyverse)
library(dplyr)
library(gmodels)
library(reshape2)
library(ggplot2)
library(viridis)

#grab all files
d <- read.table('Master-ExactOverlap-10KB.bed',header=T)
names(d) <-
c('chr','start','end','methp','cc','cu','peak_start','peak_end','peakID','tissue',
,'fold_change','gene_fpk','zfpkm','sample','overlap')
d <- d %>% mutate(AvZ = ifelse(chr=='chrZ','Z','Autosome'))
#plot levels around peaks
d1 <- d
#first find peak midpoints
d1$flank_start <- d1$peak_start + 10000
d1$flank_end <- d1$peak_end - 10000
d1$peak_size <- abs(d1$flank_end - d1$flank_start)
d1$midpoint <- ((d1$peak_end - d1$peak_start)/2) + d1$peak_start
d1$distance <- d1$start - d1$midpoint
#remove any 5mC positions which are further than 2KB from the centroid
d2 <- subset(d1, abs(distance) < 10000)
d4 <- d2
d4$distance <- round(d4$distance,0)
#divide the 4KB total region into 40BP windows (n=100)
cuts <- seq(-10000,10000,200)
ints <- seq(1,100,1)
labs <- seq(-10000,9800,200)
#Assign them an interval label
d4 <- d4 %>% mutate(Interval=cut(distance,breaks=cuts,labels=labs,right=FALSE))
d5 <- subset(d4,sample != '.')

#find IQR outliers for gene_fpk intra-individually/tissue
tis <- read.table('ATAC_Reduced.bed',header=T)
tis <- tis %>% mutate(AvZ = ifelse(chr=='chrZ','Z','Autosome'))
fpkmthresh <- tis %>% group_by(sampID,AvZ) %>%
summarize(Threshold=quantile(log10(gene_fpk),0.9))
fpkmthresh <- fpkmthresh %>% rename(sample=sampID)
d6 <- merge(d5,fpkmthresh,by=c('AvZ','sample'))
d6 <- d6 %>% mutate(Expressed = ifelse(log10(gene_fpk) >
Threshold,'Expressed','Unexpressed'))
d6 %>% group_by(sample) %>% count(Expressed)
d7 <- d6 %>% drop_na(Interval)

#calculate the median 95% CIs
stats <- d7 %>% group_by(sample,Interval,AvZ,Expressed) %>%
summarize(DOliveCIproc(methp,alpha=0.05))
#save the results
```

```

write.table(stats, file='Distance_10KB_IQR_Results-N200-Expressed-AvZ-
90IQR.txt', quote=F, sep='\t', row.names=F)
stats <- read.table('Distance_10KB_IQR_Results-N200-Expressed-AvZ-
90IQR.txt', header=T)
stats$BAK <- stats$sample
stats <- stats %>% separate(BAK, into=c('Taxon', 'Locality', 'Num', 'Tissue')) %>%
na.omit()
stats <- stats %>% mutate(Sex = ifelse(grepl('D_Ko_C31', sample)==TRUE, 'Male',
ifelse(grepl('D_Ko_C45', sample)==TRUE, 'Female',
ifelse(grepl('S_Up_H59', sample)==TRUE, 'Male',
ifelse(grepl('S_Up_H60', sample)==TRUE, 'Female', 'wrong')))))

cols <- viridis(5)
stats$Interval <- gsub(9800,10000,stats$Interval)
stats$Interval <- as.numeric(stats$Interval)
peaks <- ggplot(stats, aes(x=Interval))+
  geom_line(aes(y=Median, col=Sex))+
  #geom_point(aes(y=Median, col=Sex), pch=16, size=1.5)+
  #geom_errorbar(aes(ymin=LCI, ymax=UCI, col=Sex))+
  theme_minimal(base_size=14)+
  ylab('% 5mC CpG Methylation')+xlab('Distance from ATAC Peak Centroid (BP)')+
  scale_color_manual(values=c('cadetblue2', 'cadetblue'))+
  scale_fill_manual(values=c('cadetblue2', 'cadetblue'))+
  facet_grid(Tissue+Taxon~AvZ+Expressed)+
  ylim(c(0,100))+
  scale_x_continuous(labels = c('-10000', '0', '10000'), breaks =
c(-10000,0,10000))+
  theme(panel.spacing.x = unit(8, "mm"))
peaks

pdf('5mC_ATAC_PeakActivity-10KB-90IQR.pdf', height=6, width=9)
peaks
dev.off()

```

5mC - Expression

Overlap the data. Overlap the entire gene, then the 'gene' level (+/- 20KB), and the 'regulatory' level (+/- 1KB, not including gene):

Identify 'gene' and 'regulatory' regions from the coordinates:

```

for Tissue in $(cat Tissues.list); do
bedtools slop -i ${Tissue}.bed -b 20000 -g crow_5.6.genome > ${Tissue}.GENE.bed
bedtools slop -i ${Tissue}.bed -b 1000 -g crow_5.6.genome | bedtools subtract -a
- -b ${Tissue}.bed > ${Tissue}.REG.bed
done

```

```
#!/bin/bash
```

```
#SBATCH --get-user-env
```

```

#SBATCH --mail-user=merondun@bio.lmu.de
#SBATCH --clusters=biohpc_gen
#SBATCH --partition=biohpc_gen_highmem
#SBATCH --cpus-per-task=1
#SBATCH --time=200:00:00

for RUN in $(ls *cov.gz | sed 's/.CpG_5mC.cov.gz//g' ); do
TISSUE=$(echo $RUN | sed 's/_ADL.*//g' | rev | sed 's/_.*//g')

if [[ ${TISSUE} == 'L' ]]
then
    zcat ${RUN}.CpG_5mC.cov.gz | bedtools intersect -wao -a - -b
Liver.GENE.bed | awk '$8 > 0' | bgzip -c > ${RUN}.GENE.txt.gz
    zcat ${RUN}.CpG_5mC.cov.gz | bedtools intersect -wao -a - -b
Liver.REG.bed | awk '$8 > 0' | bgzip -c > ${RUN}.REG.txt.gz
elif [[ ${TISSUE} = 'M' ]]
then
    zcat ${RUN}.CpG_5mC.cov.gz | bedtools intersect -wao -a - -b
Spleen.GENE.bed | awk '$8 > 0' | bgzip -c > ${RUN}.GENE.txt.gz
    zcat ${RUN}.CpG_5mC.cov.gz | bedtools intersect -wao -a - -b
Spleen.REG.bed | awk '$8 > 0' | bgzip -c > ${RUN}.REG.txt.gz
else
    echo "NOTHING"
fi

done

```

Within R, extract and plot:

```

setwd('/dss/dss1egfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-
0018/projects/2021__HybridZone_Epigenetics/ATACseq_Methylation_Analyses/2021_NOV/
Clip_9_Q20/Compensated_States')
.libPaths('~/.miniconda3/envs/r/lib/R/library')
library(dplyr)
library(tidyverse)
library(reshape2)
library(matrixStats)
library(viridis)
library(ggpubr)

#grab all files
files <- list.files(path=".", pattern="*.txt.gz", full.names=TRUE,
recursive=FALSE)
mds = NULL

#loop through them..
for (samp in files) {

    cat('Reading in file: ',samp,'\n')
    #read data
    ztab <- gzfile(samp,'rt');
    tab <- read.table(ztab,header=F);

    #extract name which will be our new variable
    name <- gsub('./',' ',samp)

```

```

name <- gsub('.txt.gz','',name)
ann = gsub('.*\.\.', '',name)
tis = gsub('_ADL.*', '',name)
tis = gsub('.*_', '',tis)
sex = gsub('.*ADL_', '',name)
sex = gsub('\.\. .*', '',sex)
name <- gsub('\.\. .*', '',name)

#grab only site / countM / countU / %5mC
tab2 <- tab %>% select(V18,V1,V5,V6,V17,V10,V16)
tab3 = tab2 %>% group_by(V18,V1,V17,V10,V16) %>% summarize(mC = sum(V5),
                                                         uC = sum(V6),
                                                         mP = sum(V5) /
sum(V5+V6),
                                                         Sample = name,
                                                         Tissue = tis,
                                                         Sex = sex,
                                                         Analysis = ann)

mds = rbind(mds,tab3)
}

#calculate F/M
fm = mds %>% dplyr::rename(gene = V18, chr = V1, compensation_state = V17,
genealogfm = V10, genediff = V16)
#change 0 to 0.01 for small number
fm = fm %>% mutate(mP = ifelse(mP < 0.01, 0.01, mP),
                  mP = round(mP,2))
fm = fm %>% mutate(compensation_state =
gsub('partially_compensated','compensated',compensation_state))
fm = fm %>% mutate(compensation_state =
gsub('compensated','DC',compensation_state),
                  compensation_state =
gsub('not_compensated','Not_DC',compensation_state))
write.table(fm,file='Methylation_Over_Transcripts.txt',quote=F,sep='\t',row.names
=F)

#or start from here
fm = read.table('Methylation_Over_Transcripts.txt',header=T)
#add log2(f/m) and f-m values for methylation
fms = fm %>%
group_by(gene,chr,compensation_state,genealogfm,genediff,Tissue,Analysis) %>%
  summarize(methlogfm = log2(mean(mP[Sex == 'F']) / mean(mP[Sex =='M'])),
            methfmsub = mean(mP[Sex == 'F']) - mean(mP[Sex =='M']))

#calculate rho between each 5mC and expression state (4 total comparisons)
fmrho = fms %>% group_by(chr,compensation_state,Tissue,Analysis) %>% na.omit %>%
  summarize('log2(f/m) 5mC@log2(f/m) RNA' =
cor(genealogfm,methlogfm,method='spearman'),
          'f-m 5mC@log2(f/m) RNA' = cor(genealogfm,methfmsub,method='spearman'),
          'log2(f/m) 5mC@f-m RNA' = cor(genediff,methlogfm,method='spearman'),
          'f-m 5mC@f-m RNA' = cor(genediff,methfmsub,method='spearman'))

#make a label for plotting
rho1ab = fmrho %>% pivot_longer(!c(chr,compensation_state,Tissue,Analysis))
rho1ab = rho1ab %>% separate(name,into=c('methname','genename'),sep='@',remove =
T)

```

```

#plots
fmf = fms %>%
pivot_longer(!c(gene,chr,compensation_state,genelogfm,genediff,Tissue,Analysis),n
ames_to = 'methname', values_to='methval') %>%

pivot_longer(!c(gene,chr,compensation_state,Tissue,methname,methval,Analysis),na
mes_to = 'genename',values_to='geneval')
fmf = fmf %>% mutate(methname = gsub('methlogfm','log2(f/m) 5mC',methname),
methname = gsub('methfmsub','f-m 5mC',methname),
genename = gsub('genelogfm','log2(f/m) RNA',genename),
genename = gsub('genediff','f-m RNA',genename))

#plot correlations, here only for f-m for 5mC and log2(f/m) for RNA, change those
accordingly
fmp = fmf %>% filter(methname == 'f-m 5mC' & genename == 'log2(f/m) RNA') %>%
ggplot(aes(x=methval,y=geneval,col=compensation_state))+
geom_point()+
scale_color_manual(values=viridis(3))+
geom_vline(xintercept=0,lty=2)+xlab('Methylation (% f-m)')+ylab('Expression
(log2(f/m)')+
geom_text(data=rholab %>% filter(compensation_state == 'DC' & methname == 'f-m
5mC' & genename == 'log2(f/m) RNA'),mapping =(aes(x=Inf,y=Inf,label=paste0('p:
',signif(value,2))))),size=4,vjust=6,hjust=1.25)+
geom_text(data=rholab %>% filter(compensation_state == 'not_DC' & methname ==
'f-m 5mC' & genename == 'log2(f/m) RNA' ),mapping =
(aes(x=Inf,y=Inf,label=paste0('p:
',signif(value,2))))),size=4,vjust=7.5,hjust=1.25)+
facet_grid(Analysis ~ Tissue ,scales='free')+
theme_classic()+
theme(panel.border = element_rect(colour = "black", fill=NA, size=1))
fmp
pdf('Correlations_Expression_5mC.pdf',height=4,width=6,useDingbats = F)
fmp
dev.off()

#boxplots, here just show what the plot will look like, without significance test
fmd = fmf %>% filter(methname == 'f-m 5mC' & genename == 'log2(f/m) RNA') %>%
ggplot(aes(x=compensation_state,y=methval,fill=compensation_state))+
geom_boxplot(notch = TRUE)+ylab('Methylation (% f-m)')+
facet_grid(Analysis ~ Tissue,scales='free')+
geom_hline(yintercept=0,lty=2)+
scale_fill_manual(values=c('grey70','grey20'))+
theme_classic()

pdf('Distributions_Expression_5mC.pdf',height=4,width=6)
fmd
dev.off()

#test for significance with a t-test, implement a bonferonni correction based on
the tests done (by tissue, and by analysis reg v gene)
fmt = fmf %>% filter(methname == 'f-m 5mC' & genename == 'log2(f/m) RNA') %>%
select(gene,chr,compensation_state,Tissue,methval,Analysis) %>%
mutate(Tissue = gsub('M','Spleen',Tissue),
Tissue = gsub('L','Liver',Tissue))
fmt$Tissue = factor(fmt$Tissue,levels=c('Liver','Spleen'))

```

```

stat.test <- fmt %>% ungroup %>%
  group_by(Tissue, Analysis) %>%
  t_test(data = ., methval ~ compensation_state) %>%
  adjust_pvalue(method = "bonferroni") %>%
  add_significance('p.adj')
#t-test results
stat.test

#plot, should look the same as the above boxplot
ttp <- ggboxplot(
  fmt, x = "Tissue", y = "methval",
  fill = "compensation_state", notch=TRUE,
  ggtheme = theme_pubr(border = TRUE)
) +
  scale_fill_manual(values=c('grey20', 'grey70'))+
  xlab('')+
  geom_hline(yintercept=0, lty=2)+
  facet_grid(.~Analysis)+
  ylab('Methylation (% f-m)')
ttp
# Add statistical test p-values to the plot
stat.test <- stat.test %>% add_xy_position(x = "Tissue", scales = 'free')
ttpa = ttp + stat_pvalue_manual(stat.test, label =
"p.adj.signif", bracket.nudge.y=0.05)
pdf('Distributions_States.pdf', height=6, width=7)
ttpa
dev.off()

```

Sensitivity: Extract 5mC Data: Female Half Coverage

```

#!/bin/bash

#SBATCH --get-user-env
#SBATCH --mail-user=merondun@bio.lmu.de
#SBATCH --clusters=cm2_tiny
#SBATCH --partition=cm2_tiny
#SBATCH --cpus-per-task=1
#SBATCH --time=6:00:00

#grab only transcripts, not only exons
grep 'transcript' Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.annotation.bed >
tmp/transcripts.bed

for i in $(cat Genes.names); do

#grab each gene individually from the annotation file, output only $chr $start
$end $gene
grep -w $i tmp/transcripts.bed | bedtools sort -i - | bedtools merge -i - -c 6 -o
distinct > tmp/gene.$i.bed

done

```

And then overlap with 5mC data:

```
#!/bin/bash

#SBATCH --get-user-env
#SBATCH --mail-user=merondun@bio.lmu.de
#SBATCH --clusters=cm2_tiny
#SBATCH --partition=cm2_tiny
#SBATCH --cpus-per-task=1
#SBATCH --time=6:00:00

genomedir=/dss/dsslegfs01/pr53da/pr53da-dss-
0018/projects/2021__HybridZone_Epigenetics/Genomes/Corvus_5.6
genes=$genomedir/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.UniqueTranscripts.bed
cgis=$genomedir/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.cgi.bed
chrs=$genomedir/Corvus_cornix__S_Up_H32_v5.6_polished.CHRS.bed

for samp in $(cat samples.list); do

#overlap 5mC positions with data, and then also with CpG islands:
$chr $pos $pos $mCG $countMETH $countUNMETH $genestart $geneend $gene $cgi
zcat $samp.CpG_5mC.cov.gz | \
    bedtools intersect -a - -b $genes -loj | \
    bedtools intersect -a - -b $cgis -loj | \
    bedtools intersect -a - -b $chrs -loj | \
    awk '{OFS="\t"}{print $1, $2, $3, $4, $5, $6, $10,$9-$8, $14, $13-$12,
$17-$16}' | \
    bgzip -c > $samp.bed.gz
done
```

For the three analyses: chr / gene / cgi, we will calculate the cumulative total of count methylated sites / count methylated + count unmethylated, to give a % 5mC for each feature. First though, we will only retain sites which have at least 10x coverage.

```
source('~/modules/R_Functions.R')
library(reshape2)
library(matrixStats)
library(tidyverse)

#grab all files
files <- list.files(path=".", pattern="*.bed.gz", full.names=TRUE,
recursive=FALSE)
allnames <- NULL

#loop through them.. CHROMOSOME
for (samp in files) {

    cat('Reading in file: ',samp,'\n')
    #read data
    ztab <- gzfile(samp,'rt'); tab <- read.table(ztab,header=F);
    #only keep positions with more than 4x coverage
    tab <- subset(tab, (v5 + v6) > 9); tab$site <- paste0(tab$v1,'_',tab$v2);
    tab$v4 <- tab$v4/100
```

```

#extract name which will be our new variable
name <- gsub('./',' ',samp); name <- gsub('.bed.gz','',name)

#chromosome file
tab2 <- tab %>% group_by(V1,V11) %>% summarize(mCG = sum(V5)/(sum(V5)+sum(V6)),
                                             mC = sum(V5),
                                             mA = sum(V6)+sum(V5))

names(tab2) <-
c('ID','length',paste0('mCG.',name),paste0('mC.',name),paste0('mCA.',name));
tab2 <- tab2 %>% mutate(AvZ = ifelse(ID == 'chrZ', 'chrZ','Autosome'));
tab2$chr <- tab2$ID; tab2$Subanalysis <- 'chromosome'

#gene file
tabG <- subset(tab,V7 !='.')
tab3 <- tabG %>% group_by(V7,V8,V1) %>% summarize(mCG =
sum(V5)/(sum(V5)+sum(V6)),
                                             mC = sum(V5),
                                             mA = sum(V6)+sum(V5))

names(tab3) <-
c('ID','length','chr',paste0('mCG.',name),paste0('mC.',name),paste0('mCA.',name))
;
tab3 <- tab3 %>% mutate(AvZ = ifelse(chr == 'chrZ', 'chrZ','Autosome'));
tab3$Subanalysis <- 'gene'

#cgi file
tabC <- subset(tab,V9 !='.')
tab4 <- tabC %>% group_by(V9,V10,V1) %>% summarize(mCG =
sum(V5)/(sum(V5)+sum(V6)),
                                             mC = sum(V5),
                                             mA = sum(V6)+sum(V5))

names(tab4) <-
c('ID','length','chr',paste0('mCG.',name),paste0('mC.',name),paste0('mCA.',name))
;
tab4 <- tab4 %>% mutate(AvZ = ifelse(chr == 'chrZ', 'chrZ','Autosome'));
tab4$Subanalysis <- 'cgi'

#merge them
tab5 <- rbind(tab2,tab3,tab4)
cat('Saved to variable: ',name,'\n')
#assign it to a new variable
assign(paste0(name),tab5)
#add this sample to our total list
allnames <- unique(c(allnames,name))
}

#get names
vars <- mget(allnames)
# merge the points, keeping all
masterWGBS <- Reduce(function(x,y) merge(x = x, y = y,
by=c('ID','length','AvZ','chr','Subanalysis'),all=TRUE),vars)

write.table(masterWGBS,file='Step1.txt',quote=F,sep='\t',row.names=F)

#filter according to missingness, retain sites with no missing data, according to
tissue
samps <- c('S_Up_H60_L_ADL_F','S_Up_H60_M_ADL_F',

```

```

      'S_Up_H59_L_ADL_M', 'S_Up_H59_M_ADL_M',
      'D_Ko_C45_M_ADL_F', 'D_Ko_C45_L_ADL_F',
      'D_Ko_C31_M_ADL_M', 'D_Ko_C31_L_ADL_M')

sampM <- samps[grepl('_M_AD', samps)]
#remove sites with missing data specific by tissue
covM <- masterWGBS[rowSums(is.na(masterWGBS[grepl('^mCG..*_M_ADL',
names(masterWGBS))])) == 0, ]
#convert to long form
mdat <- NULL
for (samp in sampM) {
  cat('Subsetting: ', samp, '\n')
  v1 <- covM[grepl(paste0('ID|length|AvZ|chr|Subanalysis|', samp), names(covM))]
  v1$Sample <- samp
  names(v1) <- gsub(paste0('.', samp), '', names(v1))
  sex <- ifelse(grepl('ADL_F', samp) == TRUE, 'F', 'M')
  v1$Sex <- sex
  mdat <- rbind(mdat, v1)
}
mdat$Tissue <- 'Spleen'

#and liver
sampL <- samps[grepl('_L_AD', samps)]
#remove sites with missing data specific by tissue
covL <- masterWGBS[rowSums(is.na(masterWGBS[grepl('^mCG..*_L_ADL',
names(masterWGBS))])) == 0, ]
#convert to long form
ldat <- NULL
for (samp in sampL) {
  cat('Subsetting: ', samp, '\n')
  v1 <- covL[grepl(paste0('ID|length|AvZ|chr|Subanalysis|', samp), names(covL))]
  v1$Sample <- samp
  names(v1) <- gsub(paste0('.', samp), '', names(v1))
  sex <- ifelse(grepl('ADL_F', samp) == TRUE, 'F', 'M')
  v1$Sex <- sex
  ldat <- rbind(ldat, v1)
}
ldat$Tissue <- 'Liver'

#merge
cdat <- rbind(mdat, ldat)
cdat$Sample <- gsub('_M_ADL_M', '', cdat$Sample)
cdat$Sample <- gsub('_L_ADL_M', '', cdat$Sample)
cdat$Sample <- gsub('_M_ADL_F', '', cdat$Sample)
cdat$Sample <- gsub('_L_ADL_F', '', cdat$Sample)

write.table(cdat, file='mCG-10x_LongForm_ATAC-
22May9.txt', quote=F, sep='\t', row.names=F)

```

Distribution Summaries

```
setwd('F:/Research/scratch/crow_atac/2021-11/Ratios')
library(dplyr)
library(tidyr)
library(ggplot2)

### Begin with 5mC data
mfmeth <- read.table('mCG-10x_LongForm_ATAC-21Dec21.txt',header=TRUE)
head(mfmeth)
mfmeth <- mfmeth %>% mutate(Subanalysis = gsub('cgi','CpG Islands',Subanalysis),
                           Subanalysis = gsub('chromosome','whole
Chromosome',Subanalysis),
                           Subanalysis = gsub('gene','Genes',Subanalysis),
                           Sex = gsub('F','Female',Sex),
                           Sex = gsub('M','Male',Sex))

mp2 <- ggplot(mfmeth, aes(x=mCG,fill=AvZ))+

  geom_histogram(bins=50,show.legend=FALSE,position='identity',alpha=0.6)+ggtitle(
  'Raw 5mC Distributions')+
  facet_grid(Subanalysis+AvZ~Tissue+Sex,scales = 'free')+
  scale_fill_manual(values=c('steelblue1','tan'))+xlab('% 5mC')+ylab('Count')+
  theme_classic(base_size=15)
mp2

png('Raw_5mC_Distributions.png',units='in',res=300,height=12,width=12)
mp2
dev.off()
```

Bootstrapped F/M

```
library(dplyr)
library(tidyr)

### Begin with Chromosome 5mC data, calculate F/M first
#for F/M ratios
mfmeth <- read.table('Input.txt',header=TRUE)
mfmeth$mCG <- round(mfmeth$mCG,2)
head(mfmeth)

fmdat <- NULL
tissues <- c('Liver','Spleen')
for (organ in tissues) {
  cat('working on tissue: ',organ,'\n')
  organ.df= subset(mfmeth,Tissue == organ)

  for (site in unique(organ.df$ID)) {
    cat('working on region: ',site,'\n')

    fv=subset(organ.df, Sex == 'F' & ID == site)
    mv=subset(organ.df, Sex == 'M' & ID == site)

    vector.fm=c() # a vector per region
```

```

for (r in 1:10000) {
  #sample, with replacement, the 5mC values from this region. Calculate the
  median within-sex
  fv2 = median(sample(fv$mCG,length(fv), replace=TRUE))
  mv2 = median(sample(mv$mCG,length(mv), replace=TRUE))
  #calculate F/M, but first change any zero values to 1%
  fv2[fv2==0] <- 0.01
  mv2[mv2==0] <- 0.01
  fmmed = fv2 / mv2
  vector.fm=append(vector.fm, fmmed)
}

### getting the CI
med.fm=median(vector.fm)
CI.fm=quantile(probs=c(0.025,0.975),x=vector.fm)
fm.dat=data.frame(med.fm,t(CI.fm))
fm.dat$Tissue <- organ; fm.dat$ID <- site
names(fm.dat) <- c('FMmedian','FMlowerCI','FMupperCI','Tissue','ID')
fmdat <- rbind(fmdat,fm.dat)
}
}

mfmeth2 <- merge(mfmeth,fmdat,by=c('Tissue','ID'))
write.table(mfmeth2,file='Output.txt',quote=F,sep='\t',row.names=F)

```

And submit in parallel for expediency:

```

#!/bin/bash

#SBATCH --get-user-env
#SBATCH --mail-user=merondun@bio.lmu.de
#SBATCH --clusters=biohpc_gen
#SBATCH --partition=biohpc_gen_normal
#SBATCH --cpus-per-task=2
#SBATCH --mem-per-cpu=4763mb
#SBATCH --time=48:00:00

RUN=$1

mkdir Bootstrapped
mkdir Bootstrapped/${RUN}
mkdir bootstrapped_results

egrep -i "Subanalysis|${RUN}" mCG-10x_LongForm_ATAC-21Dec21.txt >
Bootstrapped/${RUN}/Input.txt
cp Bootstrap_FM.R Bootstrapped/${RUN}/Bootstrap_FM.R
cd Bootstrapped/${RUN}
Rscript Bootstrap_FM.R
cp Output.txt ../../bootstrapped_results/${RUN}.txt

```

Merge with the chromosome data:

```

library(tidyverse)
library(ggplot2)
library(viridis)

setwd('F:/Research/scratch/crow_atac/2022_05/bootstrapped_FM/')
d <- read.table('FM_Boot-2022-05-17.txt',header=T)
head(d)

d2 <- read.table('mCG-10x_LongForm_ATAC-21Dec21.txt',header=T)
d2 <- d2[,c('ID','length','AvZ','chr','Subanalysis','Tissue')]

#merge
d3 <- merge(d %>% select(-row),d2,by=c('ID','Tissue','Subanalysis')) %>% unique()

#add coordinates
d4 <- read.table('Coordinates.bed',header=F)
names(d4) <- c('chr','start','end','ID')

d5 <- merge(d3,d4,by=c('chr','ID'))
d5 <- d5 %>%
select(chr,start,end,ID,length,AvZ,Tissue,Subanalysis,median,lowerCI,upperCI)

#summary plots
d5 %>% subset(Subanalysis == 'gene') %>% ggplot(aes(x=chr,y=median,fill=AvZ))+
  geom_boxplot()+
  facet_grid(Tissue~.,scales='free')+
  theme_minimal()

write.table(d5,file='5mC_FM-Bootstrapped__2022-05-
17.txt',quote=F,sep='\t',row.names=F)

```

DMPs: Gene-Based

```

#in bash
#awk '{OFS="\t"}{print $1, $8, $7, $9"_"$11"_"$10,$4, $5,$11}' mCG-
10x_LongForm_ATAC-21Dec21.txt | sed 's/Spleen/M/g' | sed 's/Liver/L/g' | sed '1d'
> DSS_Input.txt

#DSS: get DMRs
setwd('~/.files/atacseq/')
source('~/.R_Functions.R')
library(DSS)
library(dplyr)
library(tidyr)
library(maditr)
library(reshape2)
library(ggplot2)

alldats <- read.table('DSS_Input-FemaleZ.txt',header=F)
names(alldats) <- c('loci','N','X','ID','chr','analysis','tissue')
#add a unique integer for each gene
andat <- NULL
for (sub in unique(alldats$analysis)) {
  cat('working on subanalysis: ',sub,'\n')
}

```

```

sda <- subset(allrats,analysis==sub)

posm <- sda %>% select(loci,chr) %>% unique()
posm <- posm %>% group_by(chr) %>% mutate(pos = row_number())
sda <- merge(sda,posm,by=c('loci','chr'))

tisdat <- NULL
for (tis in unique(sda$tissue)) {
  cat('Working on tissue: ',tis,'\n')
  td <- subset(sda,tissue==tis)
  mdats <- td[,c('chr','pos','N','X','ID')]
  mdats$pos <- as.integer(mdats$pos)
  mdats <- mdats %>% arrange(chr,pos)
  nrow(mdats)/4
  allnames <- NULL

  #loop through them..
  for (samp in unique(mdats$ID)) {

    var <- mdats[grep(samp,mdats$ID),][,1:4]

    cat('Saved to variable: ',samp,'\n')
    #assign it to a new variable
    assign(paste0(samp),var)
    allnames <- unique(c(allnames,samp))

  }

  #get names
  vars <- mget(allnames)

  #create object
  BSobj = makeBSseqData(vars,c(allnames))
  BSobj

  #import design
  design <- read.table('WGBS_Metadat-DSS.txt',header=TRUE)
  design$variable <- gsub('_ADL','',design$variable)
  design <- subset(design,Tissue==tis)
  X = model.matrix(~Sex, design)
  X
  DMLfit = DMLfit.multiFactor(BSobj, design=design, formula=~Sex)
  vars <- colnames(DMLfit$X)[-1]
  dmpdat <- NULL
  for (vari in vars) {
    dats <- DMLtest.multiFactor(DMLfit,coef=vari)
    dats$var <- vari
    dmpdat <- rbind(dmpdat,dats)
  }

  #Reformat nicely
  dmp <- dmpdat
  dmp$var <- gsub('SexM','Sex',dmp$var)
  dmp$tissue <- tis
  tisdat <- rbind(tisdat,dmp)
}

```

```

fd <- merge(tisdat, posm, by=c('chr', 'pos')) %>% select(-pos)
head(fd)
fd$Subanalysis <- sub
andat <- rbind(andat, fd)
}
ddat <- andat
ddat <- ddat %>% mutate(signif = ifelse(fdrs < 0.05, 'Significant', 'Non-
Significant'))
write.table(ddat, 'WGBS-ATAC.DSS.GENE-
10x_FemaleZ.txt', quote=F, row.names=FALSE, sep='\t')

#merge with original file
ad <- read.table('FM_bootstrapped_sub_FemaleZ.txt', header=T)
ddat <- ddat %>% dplyr::rename(Tissue = tissue,
                             ID = loci)
ddat$Tissue <- gsub('L', 'Liver', ddat$Tissue)
ddat$Tissue <- gsub('M', 'Spleen', ddat$Tissue)
fin <- merge(ad, ddat, by=Reduce(intersect, list(names(ad), names(ddat))))
fin <- fin %>% mutate(AvZ=ifelse(chr=='chrZ', 'chrZ', 'Autosome'))

#and also add start/end
co <- read.table('Gene_CGI_Chrom.coordinates', header=T)
fin2 <- merge(fin, co, by=Reduce(intersect, list(names(fin), names(co))))

imp <- fin2 %>%
select(chr, start, end, length, AvZ, Tissue, Subanalysis, ID, median, lowerCI, upperCI, medi
an_sub, lowerCI_sub, upperCI_sub, fdrs)
imp <- imp %>% dplyr::rename(pval_fdr_corrected = fdrs)
imp <- imp %>% dplyr::rename(median_ratio = median, lowerCI_ratio = lowerCI,
upperCI_ratio=upperCI)

hist(log2(imp$median))
hist(imp$median_sub)
imp <- imp %>% mutate(bias_ratio = ifelse(pval_fdr_corrected < 0.05 &
log2(median_ratio) > .5, 'female-biased',
                             ifelse(pval_fdr_corrected < 0.05 &
log2(median_ratio) < -.5, 'male-biased', 'unbiased')),
                    bias_sub = ifelse(pval_fdr_corrected < 0.05 & median_sub >
0.25, 'female-biased',
                             ifelse(pval_fdr_corrected < 0.05 &
median_sub < -0.25, 'male-biased', 'unbiased'))))

imp <- read.table('5mC_FM-Bootstrapped-Ratio_and_Sub-Bias__2022-06-
02.txt', header=T)
counts <- imp %>% group_by(Tissue, AvZ, Subanalysis) %>% dplyr::count(bias)
counts %>% subset(bias != 'unbiased') %>%
ggplot(aes(x=Subanalysis, fill=bias, y=n))+geom_bar(stat='identity')+
  facet_grid(AvZ~Tissue, scales='free')+theme_classic()
imp$start <- imp$start/1000000
ratio <- imp %>% subset(chr == 'chrZ') %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=start, y=log2(median_ratio), col=bias_ratio))+
  geom_point()+

  geom_errorbar(aes(ymin=log2(lowerCI_ratio), ymax=log2(upperCI_ratio)), alpha=0.5)+
  facet_grid(Subanalysis~Tissue, scales='free')+
  ggtitle('log2(f/m)')+

```

```

xlab('chr Z (MB)')+
ylab('log2(F/M)')+
scale_color_manual(values=c('cadetblue2', 'cadetblue', 'grey60'))+
theme_minimal()+
geom_hline(yintercept=0,lty=2)+
ylim(c(-5,5))
sub <- imp %>% subset(chr == 'chrZ') %>%
ggplot(aes(x=start,y=median_sub,col=bias_sub))+
geom_point()+
geom_errorbar(aes(ymin=lowerCI_sub,ymax=upperCI_sub),alpha=0.5)+
facet_grid(Subanalysis~Tissue,scales='free')+
ggtitle('f-m')+
xlab('chr Z (MB)')+
ylab('F-M')+
scale_color_manual(values=c('cadetblue2', 'cadetblue', 'grey60'))+
theme_minimal()+
geom_hline(yintercept=0,lty=2)+
ylim(c(-.75,.75))

pdf('Sensitivity_Ratio.pdf',height=9,width=10)
ggarrange(ratio,sub,nrow=2)
dev.off()

write.table(imp,file='5mC_FM-Bootstrapped-Ratio_and_Sub-Bias__2022-06-
02.txt',quote=F,sep='\t',row.names=F)

```